

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.6 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>Cities across the globe are intensively working towards reducing their carbon footprint, with the pursuit of climate neutrality being a cornerstone of UP2030. To support cities in this endeavour a range of tools have been, or are in the process of being, developed. This document outlines 22 tools developed from 10 organizations within the UP2030 programme. These relate to either data governance or provision of digital resources for cities to utilise when determining which tools to use. This is the first version of a broad methodological guide for the tools. This will be revised late 2025 to offer a more detailed version following the further development and piloting of tools over the next 18 months. For the final deliverable, each tool will be presented in, and to, the same standard, where prominent use of process/system diagrams, use case studies, detailed step-by-step guides and, where appropriate screenshots of tool use will be presented. The purpose of this deliverable is to assist potential users in selecting the right</p>			

	tool for their city by covering a range of important elements of these tools, ultimately to support the right utilisation of the right tool in the right place.
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Executive Summary

Cities across the globe are intensively working towards reducing their carbon footprint, with the pursuit of climate neutrality being a cornerstone of UP2030. However, the task of effectively reducing carbon emissions within the urban realm is a deeply complex one which involves not only the actions of city authorities, but the alignment of numerous different segments of society. Such alignment is essential to support just transitions towards more resilient and sustainable cities. This includes (but is not limited to) city government, residents and citizens, the private sector and academia – as well as different urban systems such as the built and natural environments, utilities and power supply and transportation and mobility infrastructure.

To support cities in this endeavour a range of tools have been, or are in the process of being, developed. This document outlines 22 tools developed from 10 organizations within the UP2030 programme. These relate to either data governance or provision of digital resources for cities to utilise when determining which tools to use. Below is a list of the tools presented in the report's subsequent sections:

Aquatec (Madrid, ES)

- Resilience strategies database and tool

Buro Happold (Berlin, GER)

- Quick checks on climate impacts (climate proofing)

Deltares (Delft, NED)

- CRC (Climate Resilient City) Tool
- Rapid CRA (Climate Risk Assessment)

LINKS Foundation (Turin, IT)

- Ecosystem Services Assessment
- Equal Services & Facilities Assessment
- Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis

LNEC (Lisbon, PT)

- Resilience Assessment Framework
- Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle
- Water-smartness Assessment Framework
- Decision support tool for alternative water sources' allocation in urban non-potable uses
- Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems
- Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse

Maggioli SpA (Santarcangelo di Romagna, IT)

- MIRA Digital Twins Platform

Mapping for Change (London, UK)

- Community Maps and GeoKey

TSPA (Berlin, GER)

- Data driven Geospatial Analysis
- Parametric Design

UCCRN (Napoli, IT)

- UDCW Simulation Toolkit
- UDCW Methodology
- UDCW-Urban Design Climate Workshop/Facilitation toolkit

University of Cambridge (Cambridge, UK)

- Carbon budget framework

The tools are designed to support better mitigation and adaptation approaches, stakeholder engagement, data-use and design, all in the name of enhancing decision-making. Each tool is described in detail with an overview provided by the tool's creators. Each description covers the following attributes:

- An introductory overview detailing why a city should use the tool
- The software, data and expertise required to use the tool
- Potential barriers to use and limitations of the tool
- The context and point in a city's journey the tool should be utilised within
- The key principles and core terms of the tool
- Any standards which will be of use to implement the tool
- A step-by-step guide concerning how the tool should be used

This is the first version of what is intended to be a broad methodological guide for the tools. This will be revised late 2025 to offer a more detailed version following the further development and piloting of tools over the next 18 months. To this end there are several elements which are yet to be fully realised in this version but shall be in the final deliverable. Chief amongst this is the lack of case study examples of the tools being utilised within cities, which feeds into the variation amongst the step-by-step guides proposed by the tool providers. There is also a degree of variation between the detail of the tools themselves, with some tools being in an early stage of development versus those which are fully mature and have been applied in other urban contexts prior to UP2030 offering differing degrees of insights. For the final deliverable, each tool will be presented in, and to, the same standard, where prominent use of process/system diagrams, use case studies, detailed step-by-step guides and, where appropriate screenshots of tool use will be presented.

The purpose of this deliverable is to assist potential users in selecting the right tool for their city by covering a range of important elements of these tools, ultimately to support the right utilisation of the right tool in the right place.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

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<p>D3.1 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1</p> <p>Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, LINKS Foundation, LNEC, Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN and the University of Cambridge</p>	<p>D3.7 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 2</p> <p>D5.6 – Learning Programme Design, Development and Sustainability</p> <p>D5.7 - Online Learning Programme materials</p>
<p>N/A</p>	<p>Mil 12 - Advisory Board key steering recommendations</p> <p>Mil 15 - Training programme successful delivery completed</p>

This deliverable has been produced to assist decision makers within cities who are responsible for implementing climate neutrality policies and approaches. This initial version of the deliverable is intended to support cities from the mid-point of the UP2030 project (M18), with the final version to be created by the end of the project (M36) – which will feature case studies of the tools being utilised through the UP2030 project. To this end, and beyond its publication, it is envisaged that the final deliverable will be available to interested party's vis-a-vis either the UP2030 Strategic Platform (ICLEI), the 'Transformative Pathways Roadmaps' platform (DRAXIS) or through UP2030's Online Learning Programme materials (UIC) as a component of the project's legacy.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AAD	Algorithm Aided Design
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AQI	Air Quality Index
CRA	Rapid Climate Risk Assessment
CRC	Climate Resilient City
D	Deliverable
EPANET	Environmental Protection Agency Network Evaluation Tool
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GML	Geography Markup Language
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering)
M	Month
Mil	Milestone
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture
TWW	Treated Wastewater
UCAM	University of Cambridge
UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network
UDCW	Urban Design Climate Workshops
UHI	Urban Heat Island
UIC	International University of Catalonia

UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index
VGI	Volunteered geographic information
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change cities are approximately responsible for 70% of global greenhouse gas emissions,¹ despite the world's population being only 56% urban.² This outsized influence of cities places a significant responsibility upon those running them to work towards reducing their greenhouse gas emissions and to pursue climate neutrality. While there is urgency for urban emission reduction, cities are profoundly complex entities, locales where numerous social, political, environmental and technological systems are entwined, resulting in any intervention being beset by multiple challenges. To this end, successful approaches towards reducing urban greenhouse gas emissions need to be systemic, by considering the varying complexities of these urban systems, and driven by evidence and knowledge. To support city governance in this endeavour, a range of tools have been or are being developed. This document is an overview of 22 such tools from 10 providers and is designed to assist cities in selecting the right tool for them.

Each tool provider is a partner within the UP2030 project and has provided the information presented in this document. This was captured through the distribution of a survey during Q2 2024, which forms the structure of the tool descriptions provided. This process was conducted by the University of Cambridge (UCAM) team. The tools were reviewed by the UCAM team to capture the type of support offered by each tool, outlined below.

Whilst this guide is intended to serve as an overview of each of the tools, this version is the first of two. There are currently limitations in information availability concerning some elements of each tool's function. To this end there are several elements which are yet to be fully realised in this version but shall be in the final deliverable. Chief amongst this is the lack of case study examples of the tools being utilised within cities, which feeds into the variation amongst the step-by-step guides proposed by the tool providers. There is also a degree of variation between the detail of the tools themselves, with some tools being in an early stage of development versus those which are fully mature and have been applied in other urban contexts prior to UP2030 offering differing degrees of insights. For the final deliverable, each tool will be presented in, and to, the same standard, where prominent use of process/system diagrams, use case studies, detailed step-by-step guides and, where appropriate screenshots of tool use will be presented.

Another limitation lies in relating the tools to other frameworks within UP2030, such as the Planning Cycle developed by TU Delft and the '5UPs' which underpin this project and offer a wider framing within which the tools summarised here can be placed. At the time of writing, both the Planning Cycle and the '5Ups' were undergoing revision and, as such, have not been used to frame this version of the deliverable. Both the enhanced analysis of the tools and their application to the above frameworks will be included in the updated second and final version, due to be submitted in month 36.

Six forms of support are offered by the tools, where they are envisioned and designed to provide better *decision-making, mitigation, adaptation, engagement, data use* and *design* (See: Table 1). Each of these qualities are briefly explored below.

Better Decision-Making

Each of the 22 tools are designed to support better decision making. This may be through producing maps to provide visual clarity to various elements of the city by mapping or simulating them, supporting data analysis or by conducting simulations of urban processes.

Better Mitigation

Climate change mitigation is an essential element of urban climate neutrality. Here, seven tools are designed to support better mitigation approaches, concerning the reduction of emissions through water-reuse (LNEC), supporting stakeholders adopt sustainable actions (UCCRN) and analysing correct mitigation approaches (Buro Happold), as well as mapping the organisational flow of carbon emission data (UCAM).

Better Adaptation

Whilst reducing and removing urban greenhouse gas emissions are required, approaches centred upon making the city more resilient and adaptable are equally as vital. Twelve tools are included to support adaptation measures. These include conducting risk analysis of various urban phenomena, from the urban heat island (LINKS) to reusing non-potable water (LNEC) as well as assessing the whole city from an adaptation perspective (Deltares). Adaptation decision support is also represented, through the selection of the best adaptation approach for the city to pursue (Aquatec and Buro Happold), as well as simulation tools to support the development of approaches to enhance adaptation through water management (LNEC) and by managing approaches across different spatial scales within the city (UCCRN).

Better Engagement

The 10 tools featured here have been developed with a focus upon working across different groups, organisations and silos, thereby supporting better engagement. This is approached in a range of different ways, from assessment frameworks focusing on the provision of equal services (LINKS), water smartness and resilience (LNEC) and the selection of approaches (Buro Happold), to running workshops to enhance climate mitigation and adaptation across different stakeholder groups (Deltares and UCCRN). Another means of enhancing engagement emerges through the use of visualisation approaches, be this community (Mapping for Change) or data flow mapping (UCAM) or the use of digital twins (Maggioli).

Better Data Use

A central component to the reduction of urban greenhouse gas emissions is the use of data to inform decision making. Seven tools have been developed to support better utilisation of urban data. This revolves around the visualisation of data via digital twins (Maggioli), community mapping (Mapping for Change) and the monitoring and forecasting of air quality (LINKS), as well as the analysis of how carbon emission data is used within organisations (UCAM), the modelling of reclaimed water quality (LNEC), the management of different types of data in a workshop setting (UCCRN) and the leveraging of urban datasets to make more informed decisions (Buro Happold).

Better Design

Improved urban design processes and approaches are another important element in the pursuit of urban climate neutrality and 13 tools are provided here to assist in this. These revolve around various

approaches, from leveraging cross-cutting data sets and systemic approaches (TSPA) and ecosystem services assessment (LINKS) to support improved design approaches, through to digital twins (Maggioli), design and decision-making tools for water systems and water reuse (LNEC), assessing the synergies between various approaches (Buro Happold) and creating designs through multiple stakeholder perspectives (Deltares and UCCRN).

Table 1: An overview of the forms of support available from each tool

Tool	Better Decision Making	Better Mitigation	Better Adaptation	Better Engagement	Better Data Use	Better Design
AQUATEC - Resilience strategies database and tool (RESCCUE product)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Buro Happold - Quick checks on climate impacts (climate proofing)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Deltares - CRCTool (formally known as AST tool)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Deltares - Rapid CRA (Climate Risk Assessment)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LINKS - Ecosystem Services Assessment	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LINKS - Equal Services & Facilities Assessment	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LINKS - Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LINKS - Air quality monitoring and forecasting	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Decision support tool for alternative water sources' allocation in urban non-potable uses	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Resilience Assessment Framework (RESCCUE product)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LNEC - Water-smartness Assessment Framework (a B-WaterSmart product)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Maggioli SpA - MIRA Digital Twins Platform	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mapping for Change CIC - Community Maps	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
TSPA - Data driven geospatial analysis	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
TSPA - Parametric design	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
UCAM - Carbon budget framework	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
UCCRN - UDCW Methodology	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
UCCRN - UDCW Simulation Toolkit	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
UCCRN - UDCW-Urban Design Climate Workshop/Facilitation toolkit	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document serves as a guide to help cities select the right digital planning and design tools to support their progress towards carbon neutrality.

What follows is a detailed overview of the benefits of utilising the presented tools, technical (software and data) and expertise requirements, any potential tool limitations or barriers to implementation and an overview of each tools key underpinning principles and core terms. This is supported by a step-by-step guide on how to use the tool (where available).

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction
- ❖ Section 2 – Overview of Sections
- ❖ Section 3 - 12 – Summary of each tool, grouped according to lead developing organisation
- ❖ Section 13 – Conclusion

2 Overview of Sections

Below is a copy of the survey sent out to each technical partner who falls within this task and deliverable. This has been included to define each section of the deliverable.

Table 2: Technical Partner Survey

<p>Why Should a City Use this Tool?</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this first section is to sell the tool to potential users. So, think of the urban issues your tool is designed to work with and how it will work to solve them. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the data outputs of this tool? • What are the associated anticipated outcomes? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are the direct benefits to a city if they use this tool (the positive impacts directly produced by the tool). ○ What are the broader benefits to a city if this tool is used (positive impacts which are indirectly related to the tool being used. For example: a new way of doing things) <p>The financial requirements to use the tool are presented here along three lines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding Required – Tool needs to be purchased to use - Partial Funding Required – Certain elements of the tool require purchasing - No Funding Required – Tool is free to use
<p>Software Requirements</p>	<p><i>For a city to use your tool, they will have to utilise the relevant software - whilst some users may have prior access to and experience using it, others may find it completely novel. Therefore, it is important for each tool's software components to be extensively detailed. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the forms of software required to use this tool? • For each item listed, please state if they are free to use or require purchase. Please provide any relevant weblinks to the providers (ideally to their price list)
<p>Data Requirements</p>	<p><i>This concerns which data is needed for your tool to function. Consider what the minimum data requirements are, as well as whether this can be expanded upon by adding more/different sources. Here clarity is of importance, so the more insight around the application of data the better. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the data requirements to use this tool? • What forms of data are required as an input (carbon emissions, demographic, etc.)? • What format does the data need to be in? • How is data to be collected?
<p>Expertise Requirements</p>	<p><i>Whilst some tools are relatively simple and iterative to use, others require formal training and expertise. Therefore, it is essential that</i></p>

	<p>users are aware of the expertise required. To this end, this section requires information about the skills and knowledge needed to use your tool. If expertise is not required, please make it clear why this is the case. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is specific expertise required to use this tool? If so, please specify the requirements. • How does this expertise apply to the tool? • Which elements within the tool require this expertise?
<p>What are the Potential Barriers which Could Prevent this Tool Being Used?</p>	<p>Every tool is designed to be user friendly within its appropriate context, yet, however well designed a tool is, there will be elements which prevent various potential users from applying it. This section is focused on these elements. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software, Data, Expertise • Cost • Time • Participants
<p>In What Context is the Tool Designed to be Used?</p>	<p>This section invites you to think about the specific elements of a city your tool is designed to work within, by considering the boundary of your tool. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope of your tool • The scale of your tool (is it sector specific, or is it intended to be used at the city level?) • Are there different organisations or elements of city governance which are covered by your tool? • Is your tool intended to be solely used by city authorities/government or is it to be used by different sets of users and stakeholders?
<p>What are the Limitations of this Tool?</p>	<p>Whilst a tool is designed to work within a designated context, from the specific to the relatively broad in scope and scale, no tool can comprehensively cover every element of a city. Therefore, this section requires you to consider the limits of your tool's capability and what elements fall beyond it's intended scope. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the scope of your tool may exclude certain elements • How the intended scale within which your tool works could limit the development of different perspectives (such as granularity at the micro-scale or 'big picture' at the macro)?
<p>Where on a City's Journey Should the Tool be Used?</p>	<p>Different cities are at various stages of developing and implementing strategies to reduce their carbon emissions. Therefore, it is important for a potential user to know where in this process they would be applying your tool and how your tool would assist in each stage. Things to consider include:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the tool is intended for use and how it would support that stage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The start of a project (idea formulation) ○ Through development cycles (prototyping, trials) ○ The use/application stages ○ Throughout the entire project cycle
<p>Tool Key Principles</p>	<p><i>Each tool is designed to work within and support different concepts, ideals and principles; such as climate change mitigation and adaption or pursuing environmental justice. However, for potential users a clear understanding of what is meant by each principle identified by you is essential. Therefore, a clarification of what is meant by each principle is required. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The key principles users need to be aware of when using the tool • A brief description outlining what is meant by each key principle • How each principle is addressed by your tool
<p>Tool Core Terms</p>	<p><i>Within each tool there will be a series of concepts, methods and technologies which will need to be understood by potential users in order to use the tool. Therefore, a description of each core element of the tool will need to be provided. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the core terms associated with the tool? • For each term, provide a brief definition of it and how the term relates to the tool.
<p>Related Standards</p>	<p><i>There exists a range of standards which support users in applying various projects and approaches to the urban realm. Therefore, please outline which standards can be applied to support potential users implement your tool. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please list any related standards that would support the user in implementing this tool
<p>Step-by-Step Guide</p>	<p><i>This is a vital section of this guide and is intended to unambiguously support the user implement and use your tool from start to finish. It is therefore of importance that sufficient detail is provided for each step. For instance, if there is a step which requires ‘data collection’, please outline which data is required, why it is required and how you think it should be collected. Things to consider include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly defined steps, which allow a user to easily understand what is required at each step • Methods and tool use required at each stage • Who needs to be involved in the solution at every stage • What is required for a user to move from one step to another

3 Aquatec

Aquatec is a water and environmental technology company who provides services centred around consulting, design services, integral project management, installation and implementation of advanced solutions for optimization of integral water cycle processes and conservation of the environment. They focus primarily on smart and efficient management of urban drainage systems, water, climate change and resilience within cities, the reduction of combined sewer overflow impacts in receiving waters and sustainable urban drainage systems as a nature-based solution or rainwater harvesting for urban uses. They possess experience of assessing the impact of extreme weather events on water quantity and the subsequent effects on urban drainage management, whilst providing adaptation measures, technologies and solutions to mitigate climate impacts on the water cycle.

<https://www.agbar.es/etica-y-cumplimiento/aquatec/>

3.1 Resilience Strategies Database and Tool

This tool facilitates the decision-making process by providing guidance to evaluate and compare the cost and benefit of different adaptation alternatives and to prioritise between different adaptation measures and strategies according to multiple criteria. It also includes an extensive catalogue of climate change adaptation measures that the user can filter according to its objectives, site characteristics, etc.

Cost: No funding required

3.1.1 Software Requirements

The database and tool are web based and can be accessed at the following address:

<https://adaptationstrategies.resccue.eu/>.

3.1.2 Data Requirements

The following data must be introduced by the user to obtain results.

Database:

1. Selection criteria to filter available adaptation measures.
2. Complete description if new measures are added (including co-benefits).

Decision Support tool:

1. The user must initially select the main objectives for the resilience strategy including:
 - a. The target climate hazard to be addressed by the strategy: flooding, combined sewer overflows, sea level rise, drought, heatwaves or compound events.
 - b. The key benefits targeted: citizen's engagement, climate hazard reduction, exposure reduction, capacity building, etc.
 - c. Type of measure: structural, non-structural, etc.
 - d. Spatial scale of the strategy: building, neighbourhood, city, etc.
 - e. Urban sector/service to address
 - f. Adaptation or mitigation target
2. The user selects the appropriate measures

3. Finally, the user is requested to introduce a weight to each one of the economic, social or environmental co-benefits associated with each one of the measures, an implementation cost and an effectiveness indicator.

3.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Knowledge on the local climate hazards and the resilience objectives are necessary to filter the adaptation measures. Also, to perform a complete assessment and comparison of alternatives detailed data on the implementation cost and the effectiveness indicator must be provided. As an effectiveness indicator it is considered: risk reduction potential, mitigation potential, etc.

3.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

A minimum set of data must be provided to allow the database and tool to perform the prioritisation, without this the tool will not be able to prioritise actions. This includes:

- Selection criteria to filter available adaptation measures.
- Complete description if new measures are added (including co-benefits).
- Implementation cost and effectiveness indicator (type and value) for each selected measure.
- Weights to prioritization criteria.

3.1.5 Tool Use Context

The database and tool are designed to be used during the decision-making process concerning the development of a resilience action plan or strategy for a neighbourhood, city or region. This can be part of a Resilience Action Plan development.

3.1.6 Tool Limitations

If the user is just looking for mitigation measures or strategies this can be also a limitation given that the database currently includes very few examples of mitigation measures, although, as explained, mitigation measures can be included if the user enters all the required information.

On the other hand, if the user does not provide the minimum set of required data (implementation costs of selected measures and efficiency indicator) the assessment and prioritisation of measures and strategies could not be completed.

3.1.7 City Journey

During the development of a resilience or climate action plan for a city or region.

3.1.8 Key Principles

Cost-effectiveness Analysis: A method used to compare the costs and outcomes of different interventions or programs. It aims to determine which intervention provides the most value for money by considering both the costs and the effectiveness of each option. This analysis helps decision-makers allocate resources efficiently and make informed choices about which interventions to prioritize.

Multi-criteria Analysis: A decision-making method that involves evaluating and comparing multiple criteria or factors when making a decision. It allows decision-makers to consider various dimensions or objectives simultaneously and assign weights or importance to each criterion. This analysis helps in situations where there are multiple conflicting objectives or when there is uncertainty or subjectivity

involved in decision-making. By considering multiple criteria, decision-makers can make more informed and balanced decisions that consider different perspectives and priorities.

3.1.9 Core Terms

Hazard: The potential occurrence of a natural or human-induced physical event or trend or physical impact that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts, as well as damage and loss to property, infrastructure, livelihoods, service provision, ecosystems, and environmental resources.³

Exposure: The presence of people, livelihoods, species or ecosystems, environmental functions, services, and resources, infrastructure, or economic, social, or cultural assets in places and settings that could be adversely affected.³

Vulnerability: The propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Vulnerability encompasses a variety of concepts and elements including sensitivity or susceptibility to harm and lack of capacity to cope and adapt.³

Resilience: The capacity of social, economic, and environmental systems to cope with a hazardous event or trend or disturbance, responding or reorganizing in ways that maintain their essential function, identity, and structure, while also maintaining the capacity for adaptation, learning, and transformation.³

Ecosystem-based Adaptation: The use of biodiversity and ecosystem services as part of an overall adaptation strategy to help people to adapt to the adverse effects of climate change. Ecosystem-based adaptation uses the range of opportunities for the sustainable management, conservation, and restoration of ecosystems to provide services that enable people to adapt to the impacts of climate change. It aims to maintain and increase the resilience and reduce the vulnerability of ecosystems and people in the face of the adverse effects of climate change. Ecosystem-based adaptation is most appropriately integrated into broader adaptation and development strategies.³

3.1.10 Related Standards

There are no related standards

3.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 3: Step by step guide for Resilience Strategies Database and Tool.

1. Identify local climate threats
2. Select adaptation measures from a database according to multiple criteria: climate hazard addressed, key benefits, type of measure, spatial scale, urban sector or adaptation/mitigation target
3. Introduce estimated implementation costs for each measure
4. Introduce estimated effectiveness indicator and value for each measure.
5. Review associated co-benefits and modify them if needed.
6. Select priority criteria to rank measures (cost-effectiveness ratio, economic, social or environmental).
7. If needed, perform a detailed assessment and comparison of different adaptation scenarios by introducing new prioritisation criteria.
8. Check final multi-criteria ranking results and make decisions

4 Buro Happold

Buro Happold is an international, integrated consultancy of engineers, designers and advisers. For over 45 years, they have delivered creative, value-led solutions for the benefit of people, places and planet. Buro Happold has extensive experience working with the delivery of exceptionally complex projects on every continent, working with the world's leading architectural practices and organisations, such as the United Nations, UNESCO and C40 Cities. Through their global community of 'world-leading' engineering, advisory and design professionals, they are dedicated to addressing major challenges in an ever-evolving world.

<https://www.burohappold.com/>

4.1 Quick Checks on Climate Impacts (Climate Proofing)

Climate change poses high risks to cities and the urban environment, that are prognosed to increase in the near future. At the same time, cities play a crucial role in reducing the global greenhouse gas emissions. The Climate Proofing method was developed to help cities and local authorities in identifying and minimizing the climate risks of urban development projects. Further, the tool offers a proven method for the development of implementation focused strategies within the specific project.

The tool is innovative as it equally addresses climate mitigation and climate adaptation. It integrates synergies between mitigation and adaptation measures, aiming that measures on mitigation don't negatively affect adaptation and vice versa. Exploring opportunities for synergies and joint mitigation-adaptation actions can help create long-term and holistic impacts.

The climate proofing methodology enables cities to address their emissions and set a foundation to build local capacities for tackling climate mitigation and adaptation. It has a methodology for integrating data on environmental impacts in early-stage decision-making processes, including the identification of which data is needed and which reference data is valid. It also defines baseline scenarios from which adaptation and mitigation measures can be developed. Outcomes can be integrated into the further development and the following decision-making process.

Cost: Funding required

4.1.1 Software Requirements

No software is required. The content is developed through workshops, analysis and evaluation of existing information and planning documents.

4.1.2 Data Requirements

Depending on availability:

Local/Municipal policies, targets, frameworks, strategies, for example:

- Climate mitigation action plans
- Climate resilience and adaptation action plans
- Energy efficiency, renewable energy use legislation
- Development strategies, local area masterplans

Project specific, depending on the project's planning stage:

- development frameworks, masterplans
- early-stage urban designs
- early-stage landscape/outdoor area concept
- site specific area indicators: total area, gross floor area, FAR, etc.
- any other early design concepts and studies o mobility strategy
- energy concepts
- material concepts (e.g., on structural designs, outdoor surfaces)

The data requirements for the implementation of the solution require information on planned areas and uses in the project, as well as information on building types and urban layouts. Further, data on location specific surface conditions and climate risks are beneficial for the assessment of project specific climate vulnerability.

With the methodology targeting projects in early planning phases, where only a limited amount of information is available, evaluations on climate impacts can be made based on reference information in case project data is not available.

For the development of project specific targets, municipal policy documents and frameworks are reviewed.

4.1.3 Expertise Requirements

A background in climate mitigation and adaptation and an understanding of environmental impacts and the drivers for carbon emissions in cities is of benefit in using the tool and in successfully translating scientific solutions into practice. A facilitator with the above background is required to successfully translate the scientific findings into practice/ implementation.

4.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The tool aims to support municipal stakeholders in early planning stages, as crucial decisions are already made at competition stage, or even earlier. Only a very limited amount of data and project-specific information are required for a possible implementation of the climate proofing tool. Nevertheless, a lack of any project specific information might cause a potential barrier in the development of targeted and effective measures. Please refer to section 3.1.2 for the data requirements that allow for a targeted implementation of the tool.

4.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is designed to be used at the pre-feasibility phase of a planned urban development project. It is designed to be integrated into the decision-making process of local authorities and can be used in an interdisciplinary context across fields of engineering, design and planning.

4.1.6 Tool Limitations

A quantification the expected climate impacts that allows for a targeted development of mitigation and adaptation strategies requires technical and expert knowledge. A limitation of the tool is therefore currently the need for an expert/ guidance to be provided in the application of the climate proofing tool.

4.1.7 [City Journey](#)

The tool is to be used in early planning phases of urban development projects on a city's path to achieve their climate goals. The tool helps to develop and implement strategies and measures within the urban planning realm that contribute to achieving climate ambitions (e.g. net-zero targets or climate resilience targets).

Typically, the tool is used in very early planning phases of specific urban development projects but can also be used for a later review of developed strategies and in the translation of strategies into implementation measures.

4.1.8 [Key Principles](#)

Climate Resilience: The capacity of social, economic and eco-systems to cope with hazardous events, trends and disturbances related to climate. Strategies for climate resilience are developed and explored in the application of the tool.

Decarbonisation: The reduction of carbon dioxide emissions through the use of low carbon energy sources and the avoidance of carbon intensive processes. Strategies for decarbonisation are explored in the application of the climate proofing tool.

Integrated Responses: Study and development of sustainable development, climate change adaptation and mitigation in an interconnected manner. Exploring opportunities for synergies and joint mitigation-adaptation actions to create long-term and holistic impacts.

4.1.9 [Core Terms](#)

CO2 Accounting: The measurement and tracking of how much greenhouse gas the considered development area emits. This is broken down into the specific sources of emissions (e.g. construction of buildings and infrastructure, operation and energy-related emissions, mobility).

Microclimate Modelling: Modelling and simulation of the physical environments including heat stress and wind to identify areas of urban discomfort caused by extreme microclimate conditions. Factors considered include solar radiation, wind, vegetation and heat retention by different surface materials.

Climate Resilience and Climate Adaptation: The preparedness towards and the ability to adjust to future changes caused by climate change in specific areas/ locations.

Climate Change Mitigation: The reduction of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere to avoid significant human interference with the Earth's climate.

4.1.10 [Related Standards](#)

Municipal standards for communal greenhouse gas accounting such as the [German BSKO Standard](#) published by the German Environment Agency

Standards for calculating life-cycle impacts including the European standard [ISO 14040](#) and [EN ISO 15804](#) for the construction sector

Standards for modelling of microclimate including [Universal Thermal Climate Index](#) (UTCI) or similar.

4.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 4: Step by step guide for Quick Checks on Climate Impacts

1. Identification and gathering of available data and definition of reference data where project specific information is not available. Definition of project benchmarks and ambitions with regards to climate mitigation and adaptation.
2. Evaluation and quantification of the main sources of CO2 emissions within a project as well as the climate risks relevant to the project based on the data sources identified in step 1.
3. Development of project specific mitigation and adaptation pathways to minimize the climate impacts within the project. Identification of reduction potentials through the assessment of the main drivers that resulted from step 2.
4. Implementation of the climate proofing pathways through specific strategies and measures.

5 Deltares

For more than a century, Deltares has worked passionately towards answering a central question: how can we keep our deltas, and coastal and river areas, safe, sustainable, and habitable - both now and in the future? They are a not-for-profit, world-leading Dutch knowledge institute for water and the subsurface, who possess experience working throughout the world and are guided by major societal issues. Deltares possesses a workforce of over 900 people, which is comprised of over forty different nationalities. Using applied research, they develop in-depth knowledge that is necessary and useful for decision making. By ensuring this knowledge is accessible to everyone, they work towards help with innovative solutions. Through building on the continuity of their knowledge base, they serve as an important knowledge partner when working with a range of partners – be it government, the private sector or society at large.

<https://www.deltares.nl/en>

5.1 Rapid Climate Risk Assessment (CRA)

The Rapid CRA will allow to perform fast assessments in data-scarce cities, allowing to understand and quantify risk in contexts where this normally takes a lot of time and resources. This allows decision makers to act faster (investments, planning, etc.).

Cost: Funding required

5.1.1 Software Requirements

The tool requires Python for the model building using HydroMT and workflow management using SnakeMake; the hydrodynamic SFINCS model and hydrological Wflow model. All software is open source and compiled model kernels are distributed as free software.

5.1.2 Data Requirements

The tool uses data for topography, hydrography, land use, landcover, soil properties, building footprints and forcing data for rainfall, temperature, evapotranspiration, coastal water levels. Global datasets are used for the first order flood risk assessment but can be replaced by more detailed local datasets where available to improve the assessment. The data is easily provided to HydroMT using a data catalogue and typically requires no or only minimal preprocessing.

5.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Hydrological and hydraulic modelling expertise

Some expertise in setting up a python environment is required.

5.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Lack of required expertise.

5.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is designed for data-scarce cities which lack flood risk information.

5.1.6 Tool Limitations

The first order flood risk assessment is based on global datasets which may have limited the output accuracy. Typically, local (high-resolution) topography and meteorological observations will improve the output accuracy but may not always be available.

A complex local context with many anthropogenic influences in the basin (e.g. reservoirs) will require tailor made probabilistic assessment.

5.1.7 City Journey

The tool is used at the start of a project to understand the flood risk for the project and potentially how the project will affect the flood risk.

5.1.8 Key Principles

Climate Change Adaptation: The tool provides insight into flood risk in the current climate as well as flood risk under different climate change scenarios. Different adaptation measures can be simulated to understand their effects on reducing the flood risk.

5.1.9 Core Terms

Flood Risk Assessment: The Rapid CRA computes the hazards, impacts and risks of pluvial, fluvial and coastal flooding.

Climate Change: Assessments can be made for present-day and future climate conditions.

Decision-Support: The tool supports decision-making by providing first-iteration risk assessments as a basis for local action: identifying risk hotspots, collecting local data to improve more detailed analysis, identifying interventions to mitigate risks.

5.1.10 Related Standards

Flood safety requires design standards for coastal and riverine flood defence systems. Urban storm drainage requires design standards for drainage capacities of urban drainage systems. These standards are typically expressed in terms of return periods of flood events and normally determined by national governments (and for urban drainage sometimes by local governments). These standards may vary greatly between countries, lacking universal guidelines.

5.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 5: Step by step guide for Rapid Climate Risk Assessment.

1. Inception: we engage with stakeholders to understand the challenges and risks we will focus on (flooding and/or drought).
2. Data collection: we collect open data from publicly available (remote sensing) datasets as input for the workflow.
3. Model domain: we consult with stakeholders and jointly define an area of interest for the model simulation
4. Workflow setup: we define the model components (hydrology, hydraulics, impact) and input parameters for each component.
5. Model simulation: we run the model workflow and produce risk parameters.
6. First order analysis: together with stakeholders we analyse and discuss the first-iteration results
7. Next steps: together with stakeholders we discuss and formulate next steps
8. Local refinement: depending on the discussion in step 7, the workflow could be refined with local data to improve the risk assessment

5.2 Climate Resilient City Tool (CRC)

The CRC Tool supports the co-creation of climate resilient designs for urban areas in stakeholder sessions by providing an easy-to-use tool to make spatial designs and immediately show the effect on resilience of the different adaptation options that are chosen by the group. It uses a conceptual urban water balance model to calculate the hydrological effects of Urban Nature-Based Solutions created by users.

The tool supports the selection of nature-based adaptation options in urban adaptation planning and stakeholder dialogues. The tool provides information on the hydrological effectiveness and an indication of the construction and maintenance costs. The CRCTool can be used on a computer to explore and compare adaptation options, or on a touchscreen for the co-creation of urban designs with stakeholders.

Cost: Funding required

5.2.1 Software Requirements

The CRCTool is a web-based adaptation support tool. Therefore, there is no software requirement other than a modern browser with stable internet connection.

5.2.2 Data Requirements

For configuring the hydrological water-balance model, both static and dynamic input are required. Long precipitation and evaporation time series and land use maps can be taken from free EU-wide datasets. These must be complemented with local data on soil and groundwater characteristics, open water and drainage capacity. These datasets are required for the basic configuration of the tool.

The tool can be expanded by providing geo-referenced background layers that can be switched on or off in the map window. Furthermore, client information regarding their adaptation targets serves as concrete goals to work towards.

5.2.3 Expertise Requirements

Basic knowledge on usage of online tools and basis understanding of climate hazards in urban areas. No specific knowledge regarding the water system is expected. A brief introduction to using the tool suffices to support basic use.

5.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The effectiveness and adoption of the CRCTool are hindered when it's perceived as an additional task in planning and design rather than a tool to enhance efficiency. Moreover, since the tool heavily relies on stakeholder engagement, its utility diminishes if the involved parties are unwilling to collaborate in an integrated planning approach.

5.2.5 Tool Use Context

The CRCTool explores the spatial planning of adaptation options (foremost nature-based solutions) in an urban district. By using a conceptual urban water balance model to calculate the hydrological effects of Urban Nature-Based Solutions created by users, these results are shown on a map interface and in an accompanying table.

The maximum project area is 1x1 km. The tool is commonly used for exploring and planning adaptation options at the district and street level. A combination of measures on public and private land can be proposed. The CRCTool is specifically of interest to urban planners, urban decision-makers, and municipalities. The configuration of the tool can be made user-specific by adding or hiding modules in the tool.

5.2.6 Tool Limitations

The CRCTool presents three primary limitations:

- Limited hydrological focus: It primarily addresses pluvial flood risk and drought utilizing a conceptual water balance model, lacking consideration for hydraulics, for example.
- Dependency on Data Quality: The precision and dependability of the tool's outcomes rely on the quality of the input data. Inaccuracies or incompleteness in data could result in unreliable results.
- Scale: The tool is primarily tailored for small-scale project areas, which must always be contextualized within the broader scope of the project.

5.2.7 City Journey

The CRCTool is designed for utilization during the initial exploration stage of the planning process. Therefore, if a comprehensive risk assessment has been conducted but the process has not progressed to the final design stage, the CRCTool facilitates a rapid scan of potential adaptation options employing Urban Nature-Based Solutions.

5.2.8 Key Principles

Climate Change Adaptation: The principle behind climate change adaptation is to anticipate and address the impacts of climate change by reducing vulnerability and enhancing resilience through proactive measures and sustainable practices.

The CRCTool relates to the principle of climate change adaptation by providing a framework for assessing and addressing climate-related risks and vulnerabilities. By utilizing the tool, users can identify potential risks associated with climate change, such as pluvial flood risk and drought, and explore adaptation options to mitigate these risks. The tool facilitates the integration of climate adaptation considerations into planning processes, thereby helping to enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability to climate change impacts.

5.2.9 Core Terms

Climate Adaptation: The CRCTool offers a quantification of Urban Nature-Based Solutions in urban climate adaptation to pluvial flooding, drought and heatstress.

Stakeholder Sessions: The CRCTool supports discussions on climate adaptation measures within diverse stakeholder groups, enhancing engagement in addressing climate challenges.

5.2.10 Related Standards

Urban climate risk adaptation standards are determined by local governments, encompassing factors such as minimum rainfall storage capacity and maximum flooding return periods. These standards vary greatly between applications, lacking universal guidelines.

Furthermore, the growing focus on integrated planning and design underscores the rationale for incorporating the CRCTool into the climate adaptation process.

5.2.11 Step-by-Step Guide

There is an extensive public wiki available with information regarding the practical use of the tool and technical background documentation:

<https://publicwiki.deltares.nl/display/AST/Climate+Resilient+City+Tool+Documentation>

To use the CRCTool for the first time, select Start a new project or, in case you already have a saved project select Open existing project (See: Appendix 1 for screenshots of this process).

Table 6: Step by step guide for Climate Resilient City Tool.

1. Map Window: The map window contains several buttons to perform actions.
2. Project set up: First, search for the area where you want to make the project after accepting both the disclaimer and copyrights and starting the project. The map will move to the selected location
3. Once the right project location is found on the map, draw an area to indicate the project area using the button indicated with the green rectangle. The boundary of the project area can be drawn by clicking on the map and finalizing it by double clicking on the last point of the boundary. A project area can be deleted with the trash button indicated in red
4. Once a project area is drawn, a NEXT button will appear to continue with the project area setup. Press "NEXT" to continue and fill out all the parameters of the project area. Brief explanations on the options can be shown by pressing the information button. Notice that you will not be able to go to the next step until you have filled out all the parameters
5. Once all the parameters of the project area have been filled, press DONE to continue. Now adaptation measures can be added to the project area. Measures can be added in two ways: Press the + measure button at the bottom of the left panel to first select the preferred measure and then draw the measure on the map: Press the draw area, line or point button to first draw an area, line or point and assign a

measure to this object. In case of + measure button is pressed an overview of all available measures appears

6. The list of measures is ranked according to their effectiveness based on the properties of the project area and the climate adaptation goal for the project area. A search field is provided to search for a specific measure. A star button on the top of the list moves preferred measures based on the type of scenario to the top of the list. The number underneath the title of the measure indicates the effectiveness of a measure based on the properties of the project area. The icons as listed below indicate to what climate effect the measures contribute.

7. In order to have more information on a certain measure, click LEARN MORE. When clicking LEARN MORE, both the effect on climate change, a short description and image will be shown. A measure can be selected by pressing the CHOOSE button

8. Then you can start drawing the measure on the map as area, line or point. The draw options (point, line areas) depend on the type of measure chosen. An area or line can be drawn by clicking on the map to add the corners of the area or line. The area or line can be finished by double clicking on the same location. A point only requires on click to be added at the right location

9. Once a measure has been selected and added to the map, the measure settings panel appears. In this panel the depth and inflow area can be given in. In case of a line measure a width needs to be given in and in case of a point measure a radius needs to be given in. Default values are provided for all settings. Additional information on the settings can be found by pressing the information buttons. In case one first wants to draw an area, line or point on the map to design the area, first select the draw, area, line, point tool in the top left corner of the map window. An area or line can be drawn by clicking on the map to add the corners of the area or line. The area or line can be finished by double clicking on the same location. A point only requires on click to be added at the right location

10. Once the element is added to the map the panel on the left will show an option CHOOSE MEASURE to select a measure for the area. By selecting this option, a list similar as shown above is presented. The list may vary based on whether an area, line or point has been added. A measure can be assigned by pressing CHOOSE MEASURE

11. After choosing the measure the property window of the measure is shown, similarly to the one presented above. Once the correct values are given in, the measure can be finalized by pressing DONE

12. Once a measure has been added the type and the properties can be changed by selecting the measure on the map. To change the shape of areas, lines and points click the element on the map and then selecting one of the corners of the element. The corner should enlarge and can now be moved on the map with the mouse. Additional points are added to the line that can be used to create new corners.

6 LINKS Foundation

Fondazione LINKS was created by *Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo* – the biggest Italian bank foundation – and Politecnico di Torino as a bridge between research and market. To this end, LINKS has been working for almost 20 years at national and international level. Thanks to the cooperation of more than 160 researchers the Foundation oversees technical-scientific disciplines in digital technology and regional development such as artificial intelligence, connected systems and the internet of things, cybersecurity, advanced calculation systems and satellite systems. LINKS are currently operating across a range of contexts, including industry 4.0, intelligent mobility, AgriTech, the space economy and smart infrastructures.

<https://linksfoundation.com/en/>

6.1 Air quality monitoring and forecasting

Developed entirely within the UP2030 project, the tool is now available in its initial version. Ongoing efforts within the project will focus on enhancing its performance and addressing any specific requirements from cities opting to adopt it.

Air pollution poses a significant challenge in urban areas, adversely impacting public health and environmental quality. The concentration of pollutants such as particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, and ozone often exceeds safe levels, leading to respiratory diseases, cardiovascular ailments, and environmental degradation.

To provide support in addressing these problems, our tool generates maps showing the forecasted concentration levels of five key pollutants (PM10, PM2.5, NO2, O3, SO2) for the upcoming seven days, along with the Air Quality Index as defined by the European Environmental Agency. These outputs provide critical insights into pressing urban issues related to air quality, allowing cities to make well-informed decisions and take proactive short-term measures to address air pollution effectively.

By adopting this tool, a city could register improvements in public health, as timely interventions can be implemented to mitigate air pollution-related health risks. By issuing targeted alerts and advisories based on the forecasts provided by the tool, cities can significantly reduce the incidence of respiratory illnesses and other health impacts associated with poor air quality. Moreover, the tool facilitates evidence-based policymaking by offering comprehensive insights into air quality trends and patterns, enabling the development and implementation of effective air quality management strategies.

Cost: Partial funding required

6.1.1 Software Requirements

To use our tool, cities will have access to an intuitive web-based dashboard that allows easy access to the tool's outputs without requiring additional software. No additional software is required as the tool is designed to be accessible via standard web browsers. The software can be hosted on-premises or deployed on cloud-based infrastructures. The computational resources required to install the full software, which includes the models as well as the visualisation platform, two virtual machines with the following specifications are recommended:

- CPU: 4 cores
- RAM: 16 GB
- Storage 100GB minimum

6.1.2 Data Requirements

The tool processes satellite, meteorological, and topographic data about the city and its surroundings. These datasets are freely accessible, so no specific data is required from cities. More in detail, conditions of employed data access are:

- Satellite data: open access without the need for an account
- Weather data: open access with a free account on the provider
- Topographic data: open access with a free account on EU Copernicus portal

If possible, it is highly recommended to fine-tune the artificial intelligence algorithm with city-specific air quality historical data available from the network of in-situ monitoring stations. In this case, cities would need to provide records from any stations measuring air quality levels in the urban area. These records, along with the location data of each station, can be provided in standard formats such as JSON or CSV, or via direct access through application programming interfaces (e.g., REST API).

6.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Since the tool is contained within a web dashboard that allows easy access to the results, no specific expertise is required for its use, beyond basic web browsing skills. Users do not need specialised knowledge or training to operate the tool, as the interface is designed to be intuitive and user-friendly. The web dashboard provides a straightforward way to interact with the tool's outputs, allowing users to view and interpret the air quality data without the need for formal training or expertise. Given the tool outputs the pollutants level, a basic understanding of their meaning would be ideal to interpret the result fully. ICT expertise is required to install and operate the tool.

6.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

In this developmental phase, no significant barriers arise that hinder cities from using and experimenting with the tool, as it imposes no specific requirements in terms of software, data directly requested from cities, or personnel training. Within the project's lifetime, LINKS will provide an accessible tool installation to enable the interested cities to use it freely and evaluate its usefulness.

After a validation phase, it may be possible that the model accuracy will not be enough to satisfy the end-user needs. This depends on the accuracy targets and specific contextual variables, such as topographic and regional conditions. In such cases, a model fine-tuning using city-specific in-situ data may solve the problem.

6.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool operates at the city level and can be utilised by all municipal offices interested in accessing forecasts of future air pollution levels. It offers a comprehensive solution for city-wide air quality management, catering to the needs of various departments involved in environmental planning, public health, transportation, and urban development. While the tool primarily serves internal stakeholders

within the municipal administration, providing citizens access to the tool's forecasts is feasible with additional considerations.

6.1.6 Tool Limitations

While the tool is designed to provide forecasts with a resolution of 500 meters within the city, the limited availability of historical data and spatial diversity may introduce errors in predictions at this scale. As such, the tool is not intended to forecast air quality at every city block but rather to observe general trends at the city level, with the ability to inspect specific areas. The inherent limitations in data availability and spatial diversity may lead to inaccuracies in predicting air quality variations at finer scales within the city. Therefore, users should interpret the tool's forecasts as indicative of broader trends rather than precise air quality assessments at a granular level. The tool's primary utility lies in providing a general understanding of air quality dynamics across the city, allowing users to identify areas of concern and prioritise interventions accordingly.

6.1.7 City Journey

Given its features, this tool is intended to be utilised at any time, and its usage is not linked to the development of specific projects aimed at implementing strategies to reduce carbon emissions in cities.

6.1.8 Key Principles

The development of a tool for forecasting pollutant levels within urban environments, leveraging AI and heterogeneous data sources, embodies several key principles that guide its design, implementation, and intended use. These principles are technical mandates and encompass broader environmental, social, and ethical considerations. Below are the key principles, along with explanations of what they signify:

Environmental Justice: ensuring that all people, regardless of race, nationality, income, or gender, have equal access to a clean and healthy environment, including the distribution of environmental benefits and burdens. By providing detailed and accessible forecasts of pollutant levels, the tool empowers communities, policymakers, and activists with the information needed to advocate for fair environmental practices and policies. It helps to identify pollution hotspots that may disproportionately affect marginalised communities, guiding targeted interventions to address these inequalities.

Transparency and Accessibility: ensuring that the methodologies, data sources, and algorithms used in the tool are open and understandable to users, and that the tool's outputs are easily accessible by all potential users. The tool is built on the principle of transparency, with clear documentation on the data used, the machine learning algorithms employed, and the rationale behind its predictive capabilities. This ensures that users can trust the forecasts and understand the tool's limitations and strengths.

Sustainable Urban Planning: planning and developing urban areas to minimise environmental impact, promote green spaces, and enhance the quality of life for all inhabitants. The forecasts provided by the tool can inform urban planning decisions, such as where to place green spaces, how to structure transportation networks, and where to implement pollution reduction measures. This aids in creating more sustainable and liveable urban environments that are prepared to face the challenges of climate change and urbanisation.

Innovation and Continuous Improvement: The commitment to ongoing research, development, and incorporation of new data, technologies, and methodologies to enhance the tool's performance and relevance. The tool embodies this principle by using cutting-edge AI and machine learning technologies

combined with diverse data sources. It is designed to evolve, incorporating new research findings, data, and user feedback to improve its accuracy and utility continuously.

These principles guide the development and deployment of your tool, ensuring that it provides accurate and useful forecasts and contributes positively to the broader goals of environmental protection, social justice, and sustainable urban development.

6.1.9 Core Terms

Satellite Data: Information collected by satellites orbiting the Earth, typically in the form of images or measurements, is used for various environmental monitoring purposes. Satellite data is the tool's primary source of information, providing measurements of pollution levels within urban areas' atmosphere.

Air Quality Index (AQI): A numerical scale is used to communicate the air quality in a specific location, ranging from 0 (good) to 5 (extremely poor). AQI is a key output of the tool, providing a standardised measure of air quality that allows users to assess the level of pollution and its potential health impacts within their city; it is calculated from pollutant concentrations using the European Environmental Agency (EEA)¹ method.

Meteorological Data: Data related to atmospheric conditions, such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and precipitation, were collected from weather data providers. The tool uses meteorological data to understand weather patterns and atmospheric conditions, which influence the dispersion and concentration of air pollutants.

Topographic Data: Topographic data is information about the physical features and terrain of a geographic area, including elevation and land use. It helps contextualise air quality measurements by accounting for factors such as terrain, land use, and urban morphology, which can affect the distribution and concentration of air pollutants within a city.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): The simulation of human intelligence processes by computer systems, including learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. AI techniques are employed within the tool to analyse large volumes of satellite, topographic and meteorological data, identify patterns, and generate forecasts of future air quality conditions based on historical trends and current observations.

Fine-tuning: Calibrating and optimising the artificial intelligence algorithm. This process could involve adjusting the algorithm's parameters to enhance the accuracy of forecasts in specific city conditions, urban area characteristics, or changes over time. This tool uses fine-tuning to incorporate additional data, such as integrating air quality data from local monitoring stations.

6.1.10 Related Standards

[European Directive 2008/50/EC](#)

The Ambient Air Quality Directive, also known as the Ambient Air Quality Act, is a legislative act issued by the European Union (EU) aimed at establishing and maintaining acceptable levels of air quality across EU member states. It sets out specific objectives, standards, and requirements for monitoring and assessing air quality and measures to control and reduce air pollution.

6.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

In case cities adopt the base version of the tool without fine-tuning, there is no set of steps needed, the forecast will be available on the dashboard, and cities will have access to it.

If cities want to exploit historical air quality data, the additional steps are:

Table 7: Step by step guide for Air quality monitoring and forecasting.

1. Data collection: Readings from air quality stations installed throughout the city must be collected over a reasonably long period. The geographic locations of the stations must also be provided. All collected data can be provided in any standard format, such as JSON or CSV.
2. Data analysis and fine-tuning (LINKS): Collected data will be used to fine-tune the artificial intelligence algorithm working behind the tool
3. Forecasting (LINKS): The new algorithm version will be used to generate forecasts that will be available on the dashboard

6.2 Ecosystem Services Assessment

Cities are trying to place nature at the centre of local policies, territorial government actions and planning that is sustainable and resilient to the challenges of climate change. The approach to design looks to the ecosystemic potential of urban transformations, in the technical urban planning and architectural fields it is to be considered fundamental in order to be able to fully exploit the conversion of spaces into environments that generate the greatest number of positive externalities understood as environmental, social and economic. Governments, non-profits, international lending institutions, corporations and all stakeholders that play a role for the future of the cities, all manage natural resources for multiple uses and inevitably must evaluate trade-offs among them.

The tool enables decision makers to assess quantified trade-offs associated with alternative management choices and to identify areas where investment in natural capital can enhance human development and conservation. Balancing the environmental and economic goals of the cities, the multi-service, modular design of the tool provides an effective tool.

Cost: No funding required

6.2.1 Software Requirements

The tool is designed for an audience with limited expertise in computer science but familiar with the disciplines of natural and environmental sciences. For this reason, the interface has been devised by the authors to be very simple and intuitive, and for each of the inputs required by the various modules, there is a convenient button linking to the theoretical and knowledge base. This allows users to locate reliable data sources and understand how the data is constructed.

Furthermore, the software does not require high technical specifications on the computers on which it is run and can be used with the WINDOWS and MacOS operating systems.

6.2.2 Data Requirements

- Ecosystem Boundaries: the spatial extent of the ecosystem (and related area) being assessed.
- Ecosystem Inventory: Information about the characteristics of the area, including its ecosystem (e.g. land cover, soil types, hydrology, socio-demographic information).
- Stakeholder Engagement: Engage with relevant stakeholders to gather their perspectives, knowledge, and priorities regarding ecosystem services.

- **Biophysical Data:** Collect data on environmental variables (e.g. air and water quality, topography, biodiversity). This information helps assess the capacity of the ecosystem to provide various services.
- **Land Use/Land Cover Data:** Obtain data on the current and historical land use and land cover within the ecosystem, including information on urbanization.
- **Economic Data:** Gather data on economic activities within the ecosystem, including market values, resource extraction, tourism, recreational activities, and other relevant economic indicators.
- **Ecological Models:** Utilize ecological models to simulate ecosystem dynamics, assess the potential impacts of different scenarios, and estimate the provision and distribution of ecosystem services.

6.2.3 Expertise Requirements

The use of the tool requires some knowledge of GIS, although not in-depth, with both input and output data being represented by geographic computer data. The tool relies on land use change analysis, so it is necessary to be able to construct land cover mapping of different scenarios in GIS that the tool will evaluate. Lastly, a basic understanding of spreadsheets is required for creating tables with biophysical, socioeconomic, and climatic parameters, depending on the module being worked on.

6.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

One of the potential challenges could certainly be the lack of technical personnel within city offices. However, this is somewhat mitigated through the knowledge transfer provided during the tool implementation phase and through dialogue with the relevant stakeholders for conducting internal project assessments. This knowledge can then be applied in the future once the method is learned.

6.2.5 Tool Use Context

The design of urban spaces today cannot ignore the conscious understanding of the indirect impacts on the potential ecosystem services that urban systems offer. The context of tool usage is quite diverse and depends on the importance the city places on ecosystem services. For instance, it can provide a post-assessment following the creation of the general urban plan to evaluate the actual improvement and enhancement of the starting conditions. At the urban scale, this assessment can be reported on institutional information portals for citizens to understand the city's capacity to provide services. Furthermore, at the neighbourhood or transformation area scale, it can be used as a comparative tool that sets objective criteria to evaluate the best design alternatives and the selection of the most advantageous and ecosystem-beneficial design proposal in competition phases. In general, its use can range from the preventive planning phase or in accompanying the drafting of Strategic Environmental Assessments to the preliminary design phase of transformation or even monitoring the implementation of the executive design.

6.2.6 Tool Limitations

There are no significant limitations, as this approach is not widely used and almost not utilized at all because it integrates assessments from various disciplines, assembling fields of knowledge and providing new visions and potential interpretations of the territory to cities. The only limitation could be the availability of basic data, although nowadays, in highly improbable scenarios where cities do not possess updated geographic repositories, satellite surveying through COPERNICUS could be considered to address this, albeit remote, issue.

6.2.7 City Journey

In the construction of a future aligned with sustainable development and embracing the pillars of the project, the tool is used to validate that the choices for building the future city meet the specific needs for improving the quality of life of the population. The assessment of ecosystem services is a necessary condition, although not sufficient, to reconcile the needs of development with attention to preserving the liveability conditions of the urban environment.

6.2.8 Key Principles

The fundamental principles driving the development of the tool are represented by the approach to support the greening of cities by quantifying and mapping the various benefits of natural infrastructure for both the present and the future. By calculating relevant biophysical and socioeconomic parameters for a variety of decisions in data-rich or data-scarce contexts, it is demonstrated how spatially explicit information on the benefits of nature improves urban management by enhancing economic evaluation, prioritizing land use change, and promoting inclusive planning and dialogue with stakeholders.

6.2.9 Core Terms

Ecosystem Services: The functions and benefits provided by ecosystems, such as air purification, climate regulation, and natural resource provision, considered in urban planning to promote environmental sustainability and human well-being.

Natural capital: The natural resources and environmental assets within an urban area, such as forests, waterways, and natural habitats, which provide essential ecosystem benefits to urban life, and are assessed and preserved in urban planning to ensure their long-term sustainability.

Trade-offs: Choices or decisions that result in benefits in one dimension or sector of urban planning at the expense of others, where the benefits of one action may entail sacrifices in another area, requiring careful and balanced assessment of urban priorities.

Spatial Assessments: Evaluations and analyses of the spatial and territorial characteristics of an urban area, including the distribution of resources, infrastructure, population, and environmental impacts, used to understand the dynamics and needs of the territory in urban planning.

Biophysical Modelling: The creation and analysis of mathematical and computational models that simulate physical and biological processes in the urban environment, including energy flows, water cycle, ecosystems, used to predict impacts and inform decisions in urban planning.

Socio-Economic Modelling: The creation and analysis of models representing interactions between social and economic factors in an urban context, such as demographics, employment, income, and access to services, to understand social and economic dynamics and guide urban planning.

Nature-based Approaches: Approaches and strategies in urban planning that integrate and harness nature and urban ecosystems, such as parks, wetlands, and vegetation, to mitigate environmental risks, improve quality of life, and promote urban sustainability.

Ecological Spatial Planning: The urban planning process that considers and integrates ecological and environmental aspects into decisions regarding the distribution and development of urban land, aiming to protect biodiversity, preserve natural habitats, and promote urban resilience.

6.2.10 Related Standards

Since the [Millennium Ecosystem Assessment](#), the concept of ecosystem services has gained wide acceptance in both scientific and policy circles. The Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) formed in 2012 with 118 countries as signatories to assess the state of the planet's biodiversity and ecosystems. Statements about the importance of ecosystem services have been issued by diverse groups, including conservation organizations and corporations. However, mainstreaming ecosystem services into decision-making processes remains a challenge. The current economic system lacks incentives for conserving natural capital. Challenges include the proliferation of definitions and frameworks within the research community. Nevertheless, demand for ecosystem service information is rising, with entities like the International Finance Corporation requiring such data for loan applications. As of 2014, 43 financial sector businesses had committed to incorporating natural capital considerations into their operations. Additionally, at least 69 countries have pledged to account for natural capital in national income and wealth accounts. There's also growing support for payments for ecosystem services programs and integrating ecosystem services into development projects, land-use assessments, planning, and zoning.

6.2.11 Step-by-Step Guide

While not a comprehensive, detailed technical guide, this resource offers a series of steps, helpful hints, and a rough estimation of the time investment necessary to execute an InVEST model. Time demands can vary significantly depending on the project; therefore, each step is categorized into: Low = typically less than one day; Medium = less than one week; High = one week or longer.

Table 8: Step by step guide for Ecosystem Services Assessment.

<p>Install InVEST:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Obtain InVEST by downloading it and follow the installation instructions outlined in the "Installing InVEST Workbench on your Windows computer" or "Installing InVEST Workbench on your Mac" sections of this chapter. ▪ It is advisable to also acquire and install the sample data provided. In the InVEST Workbench, access to sample data is facilitated through the Settings window, accessible by clicking the gear icon located in the upper right corner of the user interface. Alternatively, sample data links are accessible via the InVEST web page. <p>Time required for InVEST installation: Low.</p>
<p>Read the User Guide chapter for each model of interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The User Guide for each model includes comprehensive information such as background details, equations, data prerequisites, descriptions of results, and recommendations for global data sources and methodologies. ▪ This serves as the primary resource for inquiries regarding models and data prerequisites. <p>Time required to review a model chapter: Low</p>
<p>Examine the model's sample data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sample data is furnished for all models and can be obtained for installation via the Workbench Settings or downloaded separately. ▪ Utilize GIS software to visualize spatial data and spreadsheet or text editor to analyze tabular data. ▪ These data aids in familiarizing oneself with input-output dynamics and model execution. ▪ Additionally, they serve as templates for formatting user data. Refer to the "Using sample data" section of this chapter for further guidance.

<p>Time required to experiment with model sample data: Low.</p> <p>Create your own data for the baseline case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gather spatial and non-spatial model inputs pertinent to the specific model. ▪ Process gathered data for the designated area of interest to ensure compliance with InVEST requirements, predominantly using GIS software. ▪ Many models necessitate an extensive literature review for specific parameters. ▪ Refer to the model's User Guide chapter and sample data for prerequisites and data formatting examples. ▪ Also, consult the "Formatting your data" section of this chapter for general recommendations. ▪ Processing time varies significantly depending on the model input and original data format. ▪ Local data sources are preferred; however, if unavailable, global datasets are viable alternatives. The User Guide Appendix for each model provides references to global data sources. <p>Time required to create data for one model: High.</p>
<p>Create future scenarios:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ While optional, scenario analysis is frequently conducted. ▪ Scenarios often involve modifying land use/land cover, habitat, or land management maps to simulate the effects of proposed interventions or climate variations. ▪ Creating scenarios may be time-intensive, particularly if stakeholder engagement or climate modeling is involved. <p>Time required to create scenarios: Medium to High</p>
<p>Run the model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Utilize the InVEST Workbench user interface or command-line scripting to execute the model using provided data. ▪ Refer to the "Running the models" section of this chapter for detailed instructions. <p>Time required: Low to Medium, contingent upon data size/complexity and the specific model. High-resolution data and/or large areas may necessitate additional time.</p>
<p>Examine model results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluate model outcomes critically using GIS software, ensuring coherence in patterns and values. ▪ Anomalies or extreme values may indicate data issues. <p>Time requirement: Low to Medium</p>
<p>Calibrate the model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Calibration is optional for high-level screening analyses or when field validation data is unavailable. ▪ However, it's crucial for valuation based on model results. ▪ Collect and process observed data corresponding to model outputs. ▪ Adjust model inputs to align with observed data, possibly accompanied by a sensitivity analysis. <p>Time required: Medium to High</p>
<p>Incorporate beneficiaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Associate model results with relevant beneficiaries, transforming them into ecosystem services. ▪ Collect and preprocess beneficiary data using GIS software. ▪ Integrate InVEST model results with beneficiary data. <p>Time requirement: Medium</p>

Valuation:

- Evaluating ecosystem services, monetarily or otherwise, is typically intricate and context dependent.
- Gather economic data pertinent to the service and beneficiaries under analysis.
- Calibrate model results before proceeding with valuation.

Time required: Medium to High.

Communicate results:

- Present InVEST results through maps, tables, graphs, etc., tailored to the audience's needs.
- Post-processing of results may involve overlays or aggregation to enhance comprehension.
- Ensure readability and accuracy of chosen visual representations.

Time required: Low to Medium, depending on project complexity

6.3 Equal Services & Facilities Assessment

Innovative aspects to be brought into the method include linking this methodology to new paradigms of cities, such as the 15-minute city concept. This approach would readjust the conception of basic needs, recognizing green spaces as essential and considering the diverse services provided by different basic needs, including various types of green spaces like parks and urban gardens.

Moreover, the method introduces the concept of care and commonalities in urban planning. Buildings and services should cater to different needs and interests, promoting multifunctionality of spaces open to the community. This fosters community initiatives and shared services, which are often lacking in certain areas.

Cost: No funding required

6.3.1 Software Requirements

It's a spatial analysis methodology that follows a flow of interactions within a WebGIS platform, hybridizing various data while weighting their priorities to achieve an integrated assessment of accessibility.

6.3.2 Data Requirements

The data families are varied and depend on the type and size of the area under investigation. It is essential, for meaningful results, to include vector data of public transportation networks, road networks, and sustainable and active mobility infrastructure. Additionally, the location of service centres and the area's settlement and housing capacity are important. Finally, for a deeper analysis with a focus on gender, justice, and equity issues, data such as property values, crimes, and accidents should be sourced.

6.3.3 Expertise Requirements

The approach to multisectoral and interdisciplinary analyses forms the basis for conducting all cause-effect reasoning that is reconciled by the final model. Furthermore, the ability to foster dialogue and build relationships among technical sectors of the city would provide great support in defining a holistic model in the field of accessibility to public spaces for local communities.

6.3.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The limitations are essentially traceable to the city's willingness to pursue integrated planning that generates fruitful cross-fertilization among sectoral technical aspects due to hierarchical and administrative divisions. Multispectral evaluation may encounter barriers in dialogue with all relevant

sectors and in sourcing updated data, as well as in establishing governance capable of ensuring the construction of relationships and the permanence of all information to be included in the evaluation.

6.3.5 Tool Use Context

The tool, as a methodology, is applicable in every urban context, both at an overall scale and at a detailed scale of individual blocks.

6.3.6 Tool Limitations

The main limitation lies in internalizing the underlying thinking of the proposed method. Currently, a specific interface related to predefined analysis contexts has not yet been defined, which could represent a current limitation. However, this could also be an opportune moment to define a taxonomy of contextual conditions that establish the essential data to complete the evaluation. This way, the method would be structured optimally to make it adherent to the analysis context.

6.3.7 City Journey

The tool represents an approach to the theme of accessibility within the realm of urban planning choices, specifically for urban regeneration plans or revisions of the layout of public spaces, both for movement and aggregation. It provides decision-makers with a comprehensive and integrated knowledge base of the current state and what is expected from the project's development, allowing them to best define which parts of the urban system to intervene in and where within the city the greatest impacts occur due to the policies or actions being implemented.

6.3.8 Key Principles

The tool emerges as an innovative and dynamic rendition of a Decision Support System, with the ambition to become a resource that establishes a readily accessible knowledge base and analytical foundation for cities embarking on a journey of urban renewal, guided by the fundamental principles of inclusivity, equity, and spatial justice. This platform aspires to provide urban decision-makers with the tools and information necessary to steer decision-making processes judiciously and effectively, while concurrently encouraging urban design that considers the needs and rights of all individuals and communities involved. With a particular focus on accessibility and equity in the use of public spaces, the tool aims to be a valuable ally for cities committed to creating more inclusive, sustainable, and just urban environments.

Just Community: A community that actively strives to ensure equality, social justice, and inclusion of all its members, addressing structural inequalities and promoting respect for human rights and individual dignity.

Equal Services: Services that are distributed fairly and justly among all members of a community, without discrimination or preference based on factors such as income, race, gender, or socio-economic status.

6.3.9 Core Terms

Integrated Methodology: Process that combines different methods, techniques, or tools synergistically to address a complex problem or achieve a specific goal.

Spatial Analysis: An analytical process that studies spatial and geographical relationships between various phenomena, using geographic data and analytical techniques to understand patterns, trends, and relationships in geographical space.

15-minute city: An urban concept aimed at organizing urban settlements so that residents have access to essential services, public spaces, and job opportunities within a 15-minute walk or bike ride from their place of residence.

Basic Needs: The fundamental requirements necessary for the survival and well-being of an individual or community, which may include food, water, shelter, healthcare, education, and personal safety.

Decision Support Planning: A decision-making process that utilizes data, analysis, and tools to provide information and recommendations to decision-makers, guiding and optimizing the planning process.

6.3.10 Related Standards

There are no specific standards since the development of integrated assessment tools like this requires hybridizations of methods and rigorous rules of statistical, spatial, and mathematical analysis.

6.3.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The evaluation methodology outlined here is structured to guide you through a series of steps for preliminary investigation and data collection. These steps are tailored to assess the accessibility and inclusivity of various services within urban areas. It is crucial to define the scope of evaluation beforehand to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of the process.

Table 9: Step by step guide for Equal Services & Facilities Assessment.

<p>1. Define the targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify the types of services and levels of accessibility to be investigated. ▪ Tailor the evaluation criteria to meet the specific needs of the target population. ▪ Broaden the Evaluation Spectrum ▪ Expand the evaluation beyond spatialization to encompass themes such as multimodal mobility, spatial justice, equity, and safety in public spaces. <p>Recognize the interconnectedness of these themes in shaping urban environments</p>
<p>2. Key Points and Performance Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify key evaluation points and corresponding performance indicators. ▪ Utilize insights from extensive literature research to systematize indicators and describe the overall level of accessibility and inclusivity in the study area.
<p>3. Spatial Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluate the distribution of services across different areas, considering socio-economic factors. ▪ Assess how well services cater to the needs of diverse population groups. ▪ Infrastructure Availability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify urban zones lacking essential infrastructures and services, hindering accessibility, inclusivity, and sustainability. ▪ Pinpoint areas where improvements are needed to address gaps in service provision.
<p>4. Design4All and Governance implementation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gather knowledge to strategize infrastructure improvements that create an inclusive urban environment. ▪ Identify and recognize marginalized communities whose needs have been overlooked in urban development plans. ▪ Ensure that the evaluation process gives voice to these communities and considers their unique requirements. ▪ Address the specific needs of disadvantaged social groups to promote accessibility and inclusivity for all.

- Explore governance tools and participatory processes aimed at empowering diverse social groups.
- Foster grassroots approaches to urban development and integrate community voices into decision-making processes.

6.4 Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis

To identify areas in the city where heatwaves will have the greatest impact on the population due to multiple factors such as built environment conditions, urban layout, cooling capacity, and the presence of vulnerable populations, an integrated spatial analysis is required. This involves assessing urban density, the presence of trees and green spaces, the distribution of high-capacity cooling structures such as parks and lakes, as well as identifying vulnerable communities such as the elderly, children, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions. By using geospatial data and climate simulation models, we can determine which areas are most susceptible to the effects of heatwaves, enabling urban planners to develop targeted strategies to mitigate risks and protect the population.

Cost: No funding required

6.4.1 Software Requirements

The use of the tool is facilitated through spatial analysis, which integrates all dimensions contributing to individual risk components. This is achieved through GIS-based analysis and data computation using spreadsheets.

6.4.2 Data Requirements

The process involves conducting cross-analysis of data from various sources to comprehensively understand the risk factors involved. Utilizing temperature data obtained from ground-based meteorological survey stations to gauge local temperature variations. Incorporating thermal radiation data collected by the Sentinel 3 satellite constellation (Galileo) to assess heat distribution patterns. Integrating land cover and land use information obtained from satellite imagery and technical surveys embedded within the local planning tool. This provides insights into the urban landscape and its influence on temperature dynamics. Identifying the location data of major sources of heat emissions resulting from specific human activities, aiding in pinpointing areas of heightened heat generation within the urban environment.

By combining these datasets and conducting spatial analysis, a comprehensive understanding of the risk factors associated with heat exposure can be obtained, enabling informed decision-making in urban planning and management.

6.4.3 Expertise Requirements

The utilization of data and the management of spatial databases are indispensable elements for realizing the assessment provided by the conceptual model of the tool. Additionally, there's the handling and manipulation of satellite data to generate the heat island effect map. In cases where specific expertise is lacking, the map provided by the proposed model can be used as is.

6.4.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The scope of application of this tool is constrained in the absence of longitudinal population studies and spatial epidemiological research. Without such data, the identification of vulnerable populations becomes challenging, limiting the tool's effectiveness.

6.4.5 Tool Use Context

The tool has been tested in urban settings and allows for a highly detailed spatial resolution. However, this capability heavily relies on the granularity of available population data. For contextual settlement data, technical maps of cities or data provided by the Copernicus platform are utilized. Particularly for vegetation coverage, which mitigates the Urban Heat Island (UHI) risk, Copernicus data proves valuable.

6.4.6 Tool Limitations

In general, the current limitations are primarily associated with the complexity of weighting various risk components. However, this challenge presents an opportunity to further improve the study and overcome this limitation by implementing a more reliable model carefully tailored to the application context. Addressing this challenge may require greater collection of specific data, a better understanding of the relationships among the various variables involved, and the use of more advanced analytical methodologies. Additionally, an iterative approach may be necessary, where the model is continuously evaluated, refined, and validated based on available data and field observations.

6.4.7 City Journey

The approach of this tool aims to ensure that the tool provides accurate and reliable results that can support informed and effective decision-making in environmental risk management and urban planning.

6.4.8 Key Principles

The methodology draws from risk assessment guidelines endorsed by the IPCC, along with a curated set of indicators corroborated by the latest scientific research. It hinges on a risk framework that employs a quantitative estimation, examining the interplay of three pivotal factors: hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. The methodology has undergone rigorous testing, and its resultant findings mark the initial phase of a comprehensive investigation into urban heat island (UHI) risks within a specific case study. The primary objectives are to shed light on social disparities in UHI impacts and to pinpoint key intervention areas deserving immediate attention.

Risk Mitigation: The process of reducing or limiting the harmful effects of a hazard or threat, through the implementation of preventive or protective actions, in order to decrease the likelihood of accidents or disasters and minimize their consequences.

Climate Change Adaptation: Measures and strategies aimed at adjusting societies, economies, and ecosystems to current and anticipated climate change, in order to reduce vulnerability and harness emerging opportunities.

6.4.9 Core Terms

UHI Effect: A phenomenon where urban temperatures are significantly higher than surrounding rural areas due to the absorption and release of heat by urban structures and surfaces, along with human activity.

Health Vulnerability: Represents the susceptibility of an individual or a community to adverse health effects from factors such as diseases, environmental changes, or emergency situations.

Disadvantaged Neighbourhood: A geographic area characterized by low incomes, scarcity of resources and services, lack of employment opportunities, and other socio-economic challenges that can negatively impact the well-being and quality of life of residents.

Heat Stress: A condition in which the human body is exposed to high temperatures for an extended period, causing physical discomfort and potentially leading to health issues such as dehydration, heatstroke, and fatigue.

6.4.10 Related Standards

The entire methodology is anchored on the application of the conceptual framework devised by the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)](#) in 2022.⁴ This framework delineates a scientific methodology for pinpointing risk arising from environmental, anthropogenic, and socio-economic factors that interact within an environment, yielding effects characterized by mutual interrelation and dependence.

6.4.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The methodology involves several interconnected steps.

Table 10: Step by step guide for Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis.

1. First, data management processes are employed to gather and organize relevant information
2. Subsequently, indicators are normalized to ensure consistency across different datasets
3. Each indicator is then assigned a weight to reflect its relative importance
4. The orientation of each indicator is carefully controlled to ensure that higher values consistently represent higher risk
5. Next, a statistical method is applied to aggregate the indicators, resulting in a composite risk index for each spatial unit of analysis
6. Finally, the overall risk is classified for the entire city based on these composite indices

This cohesive approach allows for a comprehensive assessment of risk factors across the urban landscape.

7 LNEC

LNEC's undertakes, coordinates and promotes scientific research and technological development, aiming at continuous improvement and good Civil Engineering practice and providing services of Science and Technology to public and private, national and foreign entities. They also assist the Government in the development of public policies, providing technical support to the entities that constitute the Authority in the various sectors of Public Administration, in particular with regard to quality and safety of works, persons and assets, protection and requalification of the natural and built heritage and modernisation and technological innovation, particularly in the building sector. Since its early days, LNEC has been establishing networks and partnerships with national and international entities, giving it the ability to promote and foster the globalization of Science and Knowledge; positioning LNEC as an important partner in its area of expertise.

<https://www.lnec.pt/en/>

7.1 Resilience Assessment Framework

The Resilience Assessment Framework (RESCCUE RAF-APP) is a tool that helps a city to undertake a structured urban resilience assessment to climate change, with focus on the urban water cycle and interdependencies, providing easy visualization of results through graphical representation.

The tool enables the user to assess the development level of city resilience, also considering the contribution of strategic services and their inter-dependencies to city resilience. The services included are water supply, wastewater, storm water and waste management, electrical energy distribution and mobility. It also supports these service providers to assess the respective resilience development level of the service.

This allows the city to identify what are the main strengths and weaknesses in the city and services resilience; to support decisions on the measures needed to enhance resilience and to develop strategies considering the long-term. Its main purposes are to support strategic decision-making, development of resilience action plans, communication among different stakeholders and assess resilience progress.

The methodology and web-tool constitute an assessment tool itself with a consistent portfolio of indicators for supporting the development and the monitoring of a resilience plan for a territory or a service. The tool is objective driven. The assessment allows to identify development levels, ranging from the whole city to a more detailed assessment regarding a specific service.

Cost: No funding required

7.1.1 Software Requirements

It is a user-friendly web-based application. Access to the application is made using credentials given upon request. A users' manual was developed and is accessible from the web platform. The access to the application should be made from anywhere using a large range of devices. Relying on a web framework, the app usage does not require any local installation on the user device. The only requirement is a web browser (Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox) and an internet connection.

7.1.2 Data Requirements

The user answers to predefined questions. The assessment is based on forms to be filled in, to provide an answer or a list of predefined answers, of which: (i) only one may be selected; (ii) multiple answers may be selected. Regarding this aspect, no specific data requirements are needed. Nevertheless, depending on the assessment to be carried out, city and services managers need to provide the information required to set the answer related to the resilience dimensions assessed. Depending on the level of maturity, it is possible to consider a less or a more detailed assessment, as well as qualitative (knowledge-based) or quantitative information (e.g. information from GIS, mathematical modelling, work orders), may be used. The categories include information regarding organizational planning and management; relation and communication with citizens and stakeholders; risk management; management, operation and performance of services; interdependencies between services; infrastructure and assets, historical records of climate-related events, consequences, and a description of city services and infrastructures.

7.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Urban resilience knowledge and data-based decision competences are advantageous but not mandatory. The output is addressed to city or services managers, considering a senior level of responsibility and decision. Depending on the scope of the assessment (city, service) it may involve several organizations (requiring consultation with stakeholders within the city administration to inform the assessment) or different departments of an organization.

7.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources competences. Namely, expertise in urban resilience as it facilitates the use and results interpretation. Once the tool is flexible and provides the facility to be used in a simplified and progressive way, these barriers seem to certainly be overcome. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.1.5 Tool Use Context

This tool will be utilised to assess the urban resilience of a city or strategic service.

The approach is primarily designed to be used by city authorities and managers, strategic services operators, particularly those responsible for managing urban resilience. It can also be used by metropolitan areas, consultancy services, multilateral organizations or researchers.

7.1.6 Tool Limitations

The solution is designed to solely address urban resilience to climate change with focus on water for the dimensions presented.

7.1.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating urban resilience assessment, it is intended for use to provide a resilience diagnosis (current status), facilitate the development of resilience action plans, and assess the progress of the plan implementation. The recognition of the relevance to enhance resilience is fundamental.

7.1.8 Key Principles

By aiming at facilitating the assessment of urban resilience to climate change, the tool can contribute to identify mitigation and adaptation needs.

Urban Resilience: The ability of cities to withstand, recover quickly and adapt from any plausible hazards. Resilience to disruptive events not only refers to reducing risks and damage from disasters, but also the ability to quickly bounce back to a stable state. Besides addressing disaster risk reduction, resilience includes changes in circumstances.

Continuous Improvement: Approach focused on continually enhancing processes, products, or services. Cyclical process of planning, implementing, measuring results, and adjusting. This cycle enables organizations to systematically identify areas for improvement and implement changes in a controlled manner. It relies on data and evidence to drive decision-making. Organizations collect and analyze data to identify gaps, monitor progress, and evaluate the effectiveness of improvement solutions.

Holistic Approach: Addresses complex systems in an integrated way, considering the relationships and interactions among different components of a system, thus requiring a system thinking, which involves considering the system as a complex network of interconnected elements rather than as discrete components. It integrates diverse perspectives, disciplines, or aspects of a problem to get a comprehensive understanding.

7.1.9 Core Terms

Resilience Dimensions: The aspects of city resilience of different nature, such as the organisational dimension integrating top-down governance relations and urban population involvement, at the city level. Spatial dimension, also at the city level, refers to urban space and environment. The functional dimension addresses the resilience of strategic services, while the physical dimension focuses on the resilience of their infrastructure.

Resilience Objectives: The ambitions to be achieved in the medium-long term by the city and services, described by a set of criteria, expressing the objectives' different points of view.

Most Probable Scenario: Relates to a hazardous event that causes disruption, assessed by experts to be the most likely to occur.

Most Severe Scenario: Relates to a hazardous event that causes greater disruption, assessed by experts to be the worst case to plan for.

7.1.10 Related Standards

[ISO 37120:2018](#) – Sustainable cities and communities - Indicators for city services and quality of life. International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland. Definitions and methodologies for a set of city indicators for city services and quality of life as a contribution to the sustainability of the city.

[ISO 37122:2019](#) – Sustainable cities and communities - Indicators for smart cities. International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland. Specification and establishment of definitions and methodologies for a set of indicators for smart cities.

[ISO 37123:2019](#) – Sustainable cities and communities - Indicators for and resilient cities. International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland. Definitions and establishment of methodologies for a set of indicators on resilience in cities.

[ISO 31000:2018](#) – Risk management. Guidelines. International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland. Principles and guidelines for risk management.

[ISO 9001:2015](#) – Quality management systems. International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland. Objective-driven approach and continuous improvement principle.

7.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The approach provides the assignment of a degree of relevance to each metric: essential, complementary, and comprehensive. Based on this feature, the deeper insight assessment may be firstly carried out for the essential metrics, if a city is still initiating its path on resilience, then for the complementary metrics and further on for the comprehensive metrics. Therefore, the proposed approach enables a tailored assessment of any city, regardless of their resilience maturity, and supports the identification of a resilience development level for each dimension and for each service.

Given the adopted structure, an effective and robust implementation at the city global level requires the involvement of multiple parties, in a collaborative process allowing incorporation of the best available information. An inherent aspect in these collaborative processes is the recognition of the broad duties of each stakeholder, both in their specific roles as well as contributors to the city. Generally, objectives and perceptions of stakeholders differ according to their specific duties and aims. Assembling a multi-stakeholder team allows to consider different points of view and to improve individual perceptions of the different resilience dimensions and interdependencies. Consequently, decision-making processes are better supported, and opportunities arise for using information and resources in a more efficient way. Coordination of the whole process is key for the successful implementation of the approach as for subsequent steps in planning action and ensuring its implementation, monitoring, and revision. The following stepwise approach is recommended:

Table 11: Step by step guide for Resilience Assessment Framework.

1. Establishment of the scope of the assessment, e.g. geographical limits, which hazards, services, and infrastructure to be covered. Fill in the city profile and/or the service(s) profile(s).
2. Stakeholder identification, commitment, establishment of teams that will contribute to provide information. Define a coordinator for the assessment.
3. Definition of context of application including period, level of application (essential, complementary, or comprehensive), geographical units of analysis, as applicable.
4. Definition of the assessment system tailored for the scope of application by selecting the resilience objectives and defining the assessment criteria and metrics in the tool (from the framework).
5. Identification of data requirements, data sources (e.g., data repositories, reporting or information systems) and selection of analysis tools for supporting application of the assessment, where needed.
6. Perform the preliminary assessment and evaluate the results in tool. Calculation of metrics and respective classification providing assessment results.
7. Analysis and interpretation of the resilience maturity levels regarding the dimensions, objectives and criteria, and identification of the opportunities for enhancement.
8. Using the feedback from the team, prepare the final version of the assessment.

7.2 Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle

Decision-making in the management of infrastructure associated with resources in cities often depends on measurement. This situation occurs systematically in the management of water resources, for the supply of drinking water, for industrial purposes, for use in public services, among others. Measurement increasingly has technical, legal, and regulatory requirements that imply the guarantee of levels of accuracy compatible with consumer expectations and the capacity of the instrumentation. However, the availability of measurement values in indicators with high resolution does not necessarily correspond to the measurement quality achieved with the equipment used.

Taking the above into account, there is a growing need to guarantee the reliability of measurement results, implying that entities that manage infrastructures have the tools, knowledge, and competence to assess the quality of this measurement, knowing and correcting errors according to the calibration of measuring equipment - that is, ensuring its traceability - and knowing the uncertainty of the measurement, a parameter that allows knowing the level of accuracy of the measurements carried out.

Using this tool allows you to develop knowledge of the quality of measurement of quantities applied in resource management, with the aim of providing measurement results with confidence and traceability, allowing them to be comparable with other results for the class of problems to be studied and to assure confidence to data taken into decision models.

Cost: No funding required

7.2.1 Software Requirements

The application of this type of tools uses common programming languages as resources that allow simple programming routines to be carried out, highlighting in this context the use of languages such as R and Python. Often, some simpler models can be executed in routines implemented in MS Excel or similar applications that allow the development of calculations in spreadsheets. It should be noted that the programming languages mentioned can be used freely, as they result from collaborative processes.

7.2.2 Data Requirements

The measurement of quantities is, as a rule, translated into numerical series of values that represent the observation of a given phenomenon. The nature of this data results from the capability of the measuring instrument that is used, the associated measurement chains, the data processing and archiving procedures that format the data according to a given format.

In this sense, the application does not have pre-defined requirements for the nature of the information, adapting to the available formats, and it may eventually be necessary to convert numeric formats using known and free tools.

In the case of measurement processes whose result depends on a mathematical formulation, combining different quantities (for example, determining the flow rate by measuring the area and flow velocity), it may be necessary to implement routines that develop intermediate calculations to obtain the desired measurement results. In this case, the application allows to develop these calculations and includes validation of the computational method used.

For the calculation of the measurement uncertainty, being known the mathematical model describing the measurement process, the application provides a calculation of the measurement uncertainty budget

from the information regarding the experimental variability and its probability distribution functions of the several input quantities considered in the mathematical model.

7.2.3 Expertise Requirements

The use of the application depends on the type of mathematical relationship that describes the measurement process. In the case of measurements whose model is a linear mathematical relationship, the applicable correction is generally obtained by a linear regression and the assessment of measurement uncertainty results from the application of a function where it is necessary to carry out simple arithmetic calculations and partial derivatives associated with the quantities input.

In the case of more complex, non-linear mathematical models, corrections may require the use of polynomial curves and the assessment of uncertainties may require knowledge of programming in R, Python or another similar language, as well as the application of simulation and numerical analysis. These complex mathematical models might require high computational time and programming skills.

Therefore, some expertise on basic maths, statistics and probability is required for the application of simple measurement models and additional knowledge on programming is required to develop numerical simulation.

7.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The degree of complexity of mathematical models may require more advanced programming knowledge. As a rule, the use of structured programming, associated with the use of specific BIPM guides, allows calculations to be carried out in more demanding contexts, for example, when using mathematical models in which there is more than one output quantity.

The application of the proposed approach may, in some circumstances, require a high programming time, although practical experience in numerous applications does not record situations of difficulty in data processing, even in situations with models exhibiting a greater degree of complexity.

In general, a significant part of the problems in the context of this project are classified as having a reduced level of complexity, verifying that a significant part of these can be developed using programming in spreadsheets, using pre-defined tools. in support applications of this type.

7.2.5 Tool Use Context

The tool can be applied to any type of problem that involves the direct measurement of a quantity or indirectly, making use of any type of mathematical relationship between the input quantities.

In this sense, there are no known limitations to its application. However, the use of this type of procedures requires some experience from users with regards to the metrological characterization of the measurement process, since it is necessary to obtain information about the sources of error and uncertainty to quantify their contributions to the uncertainty budget.

Regarding the use of this tool, it should be used at different levels of operation, namely, at technical level to provide an insight of the raw data and processed data quality, at management level to assure the confidence of information based on measurements used in decision-making and in the market relations, to provide confidence to users and consumers, especially when trade is established.

7.2.6 Tool Limitations

The use of programs for developing spreadsheets and implementing numerical computing routines is currently facilitated by using collaborative solutions. In this sense, it is not considered that there are financial limitations to the availability of these tools. Basic training in the application of mathematical procedures and the concepts of statistics and probability is essential to ensure an adequate assessment of the information necessary to implement calculation routines and the appropriate interpretation of the results obtained by these routines.

7.2.7 City Journey

The proposed tool should be used in any circumstance where measurement plays a relevant role, namely, in conditions of monitoring system performance, in situations of assessing risk conditions, in the context of billing, in the context of conformity assessment, for example, associated with compliance with parameters established in regulation, and in water balance contexts.

7.2.8 Key Principles

Measurement: impacts a set of processes associated with resource management, playing an important role in decision-making and understanding the dynamics of systems and infrastructures. Identifying and correcting errors and assessing measurement uncertainties contributes to the confidence of measurement results and promotes safety, essential values for consumers and citizens. Fundamental principles associated with the measurement of quantities in the urban water cycle have been identified, such as:

Accuracy: Measurements must be precise and reflect the actual conditions of the urban water cycle. This implies the use of calibrated equipment and compliance with defined procedures to minimise errors resulting from measurements and data analysis.

Integration of quantities: The measurements to be made and integrated into the various components of the urban water cycle, including water supply, distribution, wastewater collection, treatment, and reuse, will provide a comprehensive understanding of water resources and support decision-making.

Resilience: Development of measurement systems adaptable to environmental changes, technological advances, and unforeseen events.

Sustainability: Measurements should consider the long-term sustainability of water resources and infrastructure. This includes monitoring environmental impacts, optimising resource use, and promoting water conservation and efficiency measures.

Continuous improvement: The measurement procedures adopted in the measurements to be carried out must be continuously evaluated and improved based on technological advances and changing needs.

7.2.9 Core Terms

Measurement: process of experimentally obtaining one or more quantity values that can reasonably be attributed to a quantity

Measurement Uncertainty: Non-negative parameter characterizing the dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used. Measurement uncertainty includes components arising from systematic effects, such as components associated with corrections and the assigned quantity values of measurement standards, as well as the definitional uncertainty.

Traceability: Property of a measurement result whereby the result can be related to a reference through a documented unbroken chain of calibrations.

7.2.10 Related Standards

[JCGM 100:2008\(E\)](#) –Evaluation of measurement data - Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (2008). BIPM, Sèvres (France)

[JCGM 101:2008](#) - Supplement 1 to the “Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement” - Propagation of distributions using a Monte Carlo method (2008). BIPM, Sèvres (France)

[JCGM 102:2011](#) - Supplement 2 to the “Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement” - Extension to any number of output quantities (2011). BIPM, Sèvres (France).

[JCGM 106:2012](#) - The role of measurement uncertainty in conformity assessment (2012). BIPM, Sèvres (France).

[JCGM GUM-1:2023](#) - Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement — Part 1: Introduction (2023). BIPM, Sèvres (France).

[JCGM GUM-6:2020](#) - Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement — Part 6: Developing and using measurement models (2020). BIPM, Sèvres (France)

VIM: International Vocabulary of Metrology. [JCGM 200:2012](#) - International Vocabulary of Metrology - Basic and general concepts and associated terms (2012). BIPM, Sèvres (France).

Annotated VIM3 VIM definitions with informative annotations**. developed exclusively by JCGM-WG2

7.2.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The procedure described below reflects the set of technical operations usually applied in measurement qualification processes against internal, regulatory or commercial criteria established between stakeholders:

Table 12: Step by step guide for Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle.

1. Identify the measurement process to be evaluated and the system or infrastructure in which it is integrated
2. Describe the mathematical model applicable to the measurement process and its input quantities
3. Carry out the metrological characterization of the instrumentation used to determine the quantities, including their traceability, the errors obtained in calibration and the applicable corrections, the sources of uncertainty for each quantity measurement
4. Determine the variability of values associated with the identified sources of uncertainty and the probability distribution function that allows their quantification
5. Promote the calculation of the combined measurement uncertainty, using the appropriate calculation method, to obtain the standard uncertainty of the output quantity(s)
6. Determine the expansion measurement uncertainty associated with the measurement results
7. Apply decision criteria and rules, when there are limit values or applicable tolerances, defined in regulations or legislation, or defined by entities as acceptance criteria in view of the desired accuracy or agreed with customers

7.3 Water-smartness Assessment Framework

The Water-smartness Assessment Framework is a holistic framework to support multi-stakeholder and strategic decision-making towards the transition to a water-smart society. It may be used at different scales (local, city, metropolitan, regional). It uses indicators to assess water-smartness addressing technical, economic (circular economy), societal (governance, policy, acceptability), environmental, and risk dimensions. It is grounded on existing established frameworks and tailored to support UN SDGs.

Using an integrated approach, the framework aspires to constitute an assessment tool to be applied at the strategic level of decision-making. It is designed as objective-driven with a tree-model composed by objectives, assessment criteria and metrics which can be selected by the users to develop tailored assessments. The tool allows measuring the performance towards five strategic objectives “Ensuring water for all relevant uses”, “Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society”, “Boosting value creation around water”, “Promoting adaptive change towards resilient infrastructure”, and “Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation.

This allows to identify what are the main strengths and weaknesses; to support decisions on the measures needed to achieve a water smarter society and to develop strategies considering the long-term. Its main purposes are to support strategic decision-making, development of strategic plans, communication among different stakeholders and assess progress.

Cost: No funding required

7.3.1 Software Requirements

As a framework no software requirements are needed. The web-tool is being implemented in a user-friendly web-based application. Access to the application is made using credentials given upon request. Relying on a web framework, the app usage does not require any local installation on the user device. The only requirement is a web browser (Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox) and an internet connection.

7.3.2 Data Requirements

The categories include information regarding water volumes data (e.g. abstraction, consumption, environmental flow, treated wastewater, reclaimed water produced, reclaimed water used); physical assets data (e.g., length of pipes, number of discharge structures, storage tanks volume, treatment capacity); operational data (e.g., number of water samples analysed, water footprint, carbon footprint, energy used, nutrients recovered); demography and users attributes data (e.g., number of households, area served, number of industries served, population); quality of service data (number of customers covered), business and financial data (e.g., number of green jobs, revenues, investment).

Even if you need to provide the required data input for the assessment, no specific data requirements are needed to use the tool.

7.3.3 Expertise Requirements

Strategic planning and data-based decision competences are advantageous but not mandatory. It is a flexible assessment framework adjustable to different types of organizations, scale, and contexts. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.3.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Requires the correct input data to be available. It is a flexible assessment framework adjustable to different type of organizations, scale, and contexts. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.3.5 Tool Use Context

This tool will be utilised to assess the water smartness at different scales, local, city, metropolitan, regional. It is primarily designed to be used by region or city authorities and managers, strategic services operators. It can also be used by metropolitan areas, consultancy services, multilateral organizations or researchers.

7.3.6 Tool Limitations

The tool is limited in that it is designed to solely addresses water-related issues.

7.3.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating water-smartness assessment, it is intended for use to provide a diagnosis (current status), facilitate the development of strategic plans to establish the path toward a water-smarter society, and assess the progress of the plan implementation.

7.3.8 Key Principles

By aiming at facilitating the assessment of water smartness, the tool can contribute to identify needs and solutions to promote water-related circularity.

Water-Smart Society: "Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses, safeguard ecosystems and their services to society, boost value creation around water, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure."⁵

Systems Thinking: A special consideration of the interrelations and connections between seemingly separate elements and services of the city or region, in order to create more holistic approaches towards a water smarter society.

Desiloisation: Supporting the sharing of data and resources, and insight between different strategic services, groups, departments and organisations to provide awareness, collaboration and a wider range of information to support more holistic approaches to promote water-related circularity towards a water smart society.

7.3.9 Core Terms

Strategic Objectives: The ambitions that organizations, cities, or regions aim to achieve. Objectives must be clear and concise, as well as ambitious, feasible and compatible, and take into account the ultimate goal for the utility of achieving the "water-smart" vision.

Criteria: Points of view that allow for the assessment of the objectives. For each criterion, metrics must be selected for targets to be set, and for further monitoring of the results.

Metrics: The specific parameters or functions used to assess criteria quantitatively or qualitatively; metrics can be indicators, indices, or levels. Performance Indicators are typically expressed as ratios between

variables; these may be commensurate (e.g., %) or non-commensurate (e.g., \$/m³). Performance indices are quantitative, commensurate metrics incorporating an intrinsic judgment of performance in their formulation. Performance levels, which are performance metrics of a qualitative nature, expressed in discrete categories (e.g., good, fair, poor).

Reference Values: Values defined to allow a classification or judgement of what is good, fair, and poor for each quantitative performance metric.

7.3.10 Related Standards

[ISO 16075](#) (parts 1 to 5) Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland.

[ISO 20426:2018](#) - Guidelines for risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document aims to serve as technical guidelines for the assessment and management of the health risks associated with pathogens contained in reclaimed water, which are expected to be caused by the use of reclaimed water, and/or by the production, storage, and transportation of reclaimed water. This document is applicable to the use of reclaimed water made from any source water (i.e. raw sanitary sewage; treated municipal wastewater; industrial wastewater; stormwater potentially influenced by sewage) and for non-potable water reuse.

[ISO 20761:2018](#) Water reuse in urban areas. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document provides water reuse safety evaluation and public acceptance parameters and methods for users who design, manage, and/or oversee the non-potable water reuse schemes or activities in urban areas from the viewpoint of water quality. The document can be used in various stages of non-potable water reuse projects such as design, operation, and post assessment. The document is applicable to non-potable water reuse in urban areas with reclaimed water from municipal wastewater sources. The wastewater sources can also include a limited contribution of industrial wastewater input. While some communities are turning to potable reuse to meet water supply needs, discussion of safety evaluation of potable reuse is outside the scope of this document.

[ISO 20760-1:2018](#) — Water reuse in urban areas — Part 1: Design principle of a centralised water reuse system. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. Provides guidelines for the planning and design of centralized water reuse systems and water reuse applications in urban areas.

7.3.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 13: Step by step guide for Water-smartness Assessment Framework.

1. Establishment of the scope of the assessment, e.g. level of application (regional, city or utility/organization), which water services are included and the geographical limits.
2. Stakeholder identification, commitment, establishment of teams.
3. Definition of the assessment system tailored for the scope of application by selecting the strategic objectives and defining the assessment criteria and metrics, from the framework. It is a crucial stage to know where the organization stands, set up clear directions of action, as well as accountability of results through timely review. It consists of the definition, by the strategic management decision level, of (i) clear objectives, (ii) assessment criteria that translate the objectives into the relevant points of view, (iii) metrics to assess them, and (iv) reference values for every metric. Once the metrics have been

selected, it is important to check their measurement details, such as definitions, measurement units, and data needed for their calculation, and to identify who collects the data and the frequency of data collection.

4. Identification of data requirements, data sources (e.g., data repositories, reporting or information systems) and selection of analysis tools for supporting application of the assessment.

5. Calculation of metrics and respective classification (good, fair and poor) providing assessment results.

6. Analysis and interpretation of the assessment results regarding the objectives, criteria and metrics, and identification of the opportunities for improvement.

7.4 Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources

This tool implements a novel matchmaking framework for formulating, assessing and prioritizing candidate combinations of two or more supplies, including reclaimed water, in satisfying non potable water demands in urban or regional contexts, to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options. Thus, this tool aims support urban management authorities and water utilities in making smart and climate resilient water decisions for an efficient water-energy-nutrient balance in the city including safe water reuse, by enabling direct comparison of alternatives for matching water supply and water demand to satisfy specific non potable uses. It enables the decision-makers to overcome barriers which are related to the incipient experience on water reuse projects, namely, design, licensing, and long-term planning needed to support the required investments in municipal infrastructures. It is also important to have in mind the contribution of water supply-demand management to specific goals, such as energy neutrality and climate action.

This tool is designed to primarily assist water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts in two ways: 1) by providing standardized means to combine and assess water source combinations to satisfy specific demands, and 2) contributing on the technical feasibility by prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options on water management and the economic feasibility.

The tool outcome is measured by 3 KPIs from the B-WaterSmart Assessment framework⁶ - whose reference values depend on water scarcity, which is expressed by the water exploitation index plus, WEI+; the higher the scarcity, the higher the water reuse must be for a given performance - Compliant reclaimed water [%], Reclaimed water in non-potable uses [%] and Reclaimed water production [%]

Expected positive impacts measured by increased values of the KPIs on, the physical access to water for irrigation, the physical access to water supply for industrial use and the physical access to drinking water supply in public spaces for quality of life. By aiming at facilitating safe use of reclaimed water the tool can contribute to mitigate the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to its impacts by enhancing water resource resilience and sustainability.

Cost: Partial funding required

7.4.1 Software Requirements

This tool requires the payment of a fee and can run on any computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access requiring an updated internet browser in any operating environment. At an early stage for testing

the adequacy/applicability of the tool to the city, its application by LNEC and the UP2030 city will not require the fee payment. The software provider can be assessed at <https://baseform.com/>

7.4.2 Data Requirements

Water demand/supply matchmaking:

Input data: water descriptors: volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply); related energy descriptors: energy content water (supply); related phosphorus descriptors: P concentration in reclaimed water (supply); alternatives' specific costs: CAPEX and OPEX, energy; water carbon footprint.

Background data: municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.

Alternative combinations' selection:

Input data: metrics employed to qualify the different water demand/supply alternatives (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content, geolocation); risk metric.

Background data: municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.

7.4.3 Expertise Requirements

This tool allows for a streamlined, simple-to-use analysis of supply and demand matchmaking that can be operated by decision-makers without deep technical knowledge, as well as by experts with full-depth analysis. It can be used with what-if or simplified supply and demand data for sensitivity gain, as well as with fully automated data from any available source

Engineering background and strategic planning & data-based decision competences are advantageous but not mandatory since LNEC mentoring/support/capacity building is available within UP2030.

7.4.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources skills and competences. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.4.5 Tool Use Context

This tool is deployable at any spatial scale as it applies to any supply/demand context. It can be used from neighbourhood level to the city level.

Its main objective is to promote water reuse as a safe urban resilience strategy. This is a product of the B-WaterSmart H2020 project (2020-2024) and it may be used individually or in a set of B-WaterSmart complementary and interoperable tools, namely with "Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse" and "Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems".⁶

7.4.6 Tool Limitations

Compiling information with temporal and spatial granularity for Water demand/supply matchmaking may be difficult and time consuming, but once collected the tool works as repository.

7.4.7 [City Journey](#)

As a tool aiming at facilitating the selection of the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritization of strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting, it is intended for use throughout the entire project cycle, from the planning to the application stages.

7.4.8 [Key Principles](#)

By aiming at improving decision making on the use of alternative water sources for urban non-potable water uses the tool can contribute to mitigate the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to its impacts by enhancing water resource resilience and sustainability.

Diversification: By incorporating reclaimed water into distribution systems, water utilities can diversify their water supply sources. This reduces reliance on traditional freshwater sources, such as rivers and groundwater, which may be vulnerable to depletion or contamination. Diversifying water sources enhances water security and resilience, especially in regions prone to drought or water scarcity.

Ecosystem Preservation: Using reclaimed water for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation, industrial processes, or toilet flushing, reduces the demand for freshwater extraction from natural ecosystems. This helps preserve freshwater ecosystems by maintaining adequate water levels and minimizing habitat degradation caused by excessive water withdrawal.

Systems Thinking: A special consideration of the interrelations and connections between seemingly separate elements and services of the city or region, to create more holistic approaches towards a water smarter society.

7.4.9 [Core Terms](#)

Alternative Water Sources: Sustainable sources of water, not supplied from fresh surface water or groundwater, that offset the demand for freshwater. Smart water allocation in a city aims to reduce potable water consumption in non-potable uses, such as irrigation, and to increase water reuse, a rainfall-independent water source, more resilient to climate change.

Planning Alternatives: Competing projects that are measured up, compared, and prioritized through objectives-guided metrics. The impact of each alternative is quantified over the long term, in relevant dimensions.

Criteria: Are points of view that allow for the assessment of the planning objectives. For each criterion, metrics must be selected for targets to be set, and for further monitoring of the results.

Metrics: Are the specific parameters or functions for the assessment of the planning objectives, quantitatively or qualitatively; metrics can be indicators, indices, or levels.

Reference Values: Values defined to allow a classification or judgement of what is good, fair, and poor for each quantitative performance metric.

7.4.10 [Related Standards](#)

[ISO 16075](#) (parts 1 to 5) Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland.

[ISO 20426:2018](#) - Guidelines for risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document aims to serve as technical guidelines for the assessment and management of the health risks associated with pathogens contained in reclaimed water, which are expected to be caused by the use of reclaimed water, and/or by the production, storage, and transportation of reclaimed water. This document is applicable to the use of reclaimed water made from any source water (i.e. raw sanitary sewage; treated municipal wastewater; industrial wastewater; stormwater potentially influenced by sewage) and for non-potable water reuse.

[ISO 20761:2018](#) Water reuse in urban areas. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document provides water reuse safety evaluation and public acceptance parameters and methods for users who design, manage, and/or oversee the non-potable water reuse schemes or activities in urban areas from the viewpoint of water quality. The document can be used in various stages of non-potable water reuse projects such as design, operation, and post assessment. The document is applicable to non-potable water reuse in urban areas with reclaimed water from municipal wastewater sources. The wastewater sources can also include a limited contribution of industrial wastewater input. While some communities are turning to potable reuse to meet water supply needs, discussion of safety evaluation of potable reuse is outside the scope of this document.

[ISO 20760-1:2018](#) — Water reuse in urban areas — Part 1: Design principle of a centralised water reuse system. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. Provides guidelines for the planning and design of centralized water reuse systems and water reuse applications in urban areas.

7.4.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Water demand/supply matchmaking:

Table 14: Step by step guide for Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources (Water demand/supply matchmaking).

<p>1. First, the user is asked to specify key parameters: geolocation of water demands and water supplies, metrics (e.g., costs, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content), alternative descriptors. The tool allows the import of time series from a dedicated Excel® format for the following data: water volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply), phosphorus content in water (supply), phosphorus fertilization (demand). These data series consist of the user’s forecast for the evolution of the values of these variables over the planning period.</p>
<p>2. Second, the user is asked to combine the available sources to make up the required monthly demand volumes, while complying with the energy and nutrients contents as desired. Such combinations are called “alternatives” and are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required demand volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrients contents, and cost. One or more alternatives will be designed to solve the demand problem at stake.</p>

Alternative combinations, selection:

Table 15: Step by step guide for Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources (Alternative combinations).

<p>1. Most of the metrics are imported directly from the linked Matchmaking Tool, along with the alternatives</p>
<p>2. The user can also add new metrics directly in this environment by filling out the Data Table, which contains the metrics’ values for each alternative at each time step. This applies to water reuse risk</p>

metrics (“Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse” and “Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems” tools).

3. The user introduces in the Metrics Editor the relationship between the metric’s ‘real world’ values and a standardized 0-to-3 scale that is used throughout the app, effectively turning each metric into an index.

4. Metrics may be given a relative weight from a closed list; this is used later when ranking the alternative.

7.5 Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems

This tool provides complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation for pressure flow networks and is designed to simulate the advection, mixing and transformation of waterborne parameters in reused water.

It is a tool aiming at facilitating safe water reuse by enabling a safer reclaimed water supply utilisation. The outcome is measured by 3 KPIs from the B-WaterSmart Assessment framework,⁶ whose reference values depend on water scarcity (expressed by the water exploitation index plus, WEI+; the higher the scarcity, the higher the water reuse must be for a given performance): - Compliant reclaimed water [%] - Reclaimed water in non-potable uses [%] - Reclaimed water production [%] Expected positive impacts measured by increased values of the KPIs on - Physical access to water for irrigation - Physical access to water supply for industrial use

By aiming at facilitating safe use of reclaimed water the tool can contribute to mitigate the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to its impacts by enhancing water resource resilience and sustainability.

Cost: Partial funding required

7.5.1 Software Requirements

There are two versions available: a free version and a commercial beta-version developed that allows a very comprehensive visualization and user-friendly customization. The free version resorts to the open access software EPANET and EPANET-MSX, both available at <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/epanet>

The commercial version requires the payment of a fee and can run on any computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access requiring an updated internet browser in any operating environment. At an early stage for testing the adequacy/applicability of the tool to the city, its application by LNEC and the UP2030 city will not require the fee payment. The software provider can be assessed at <https://baseform.com/>

7.5.2 Data Requirements

Infrastructural model of the network in ArcGIS or other format compatible with EPANET open-access software - Water quality model (chlorine decay) available or to be developed implemented in the EPANET MSX software

7.5.3 Expertise Requirements

Engineering background or mathematical (hydraulic and water quality) modelling skills are advantageous but not mandatory since LNEC mentoring/support/capacity building is available within UP2030

7.5.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources skills and competences. Namely, expertise in hydraulic and water quality modelling. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.5.5 Tool Use Context

The tool can be used by planners and designers to integrate reclaimed water in urban planning as a water management solution to improve circularity and resilience (e.g. to drought). It can be used from neighbourhood level to the city level.

Its main objective is to promote water reuse as a safe urban resilience strategy. This is a product of the B-WaterSmart H2020 project (2020-2024)⁶ and it may be used individually or in a set of B-WaterSmart complementary and interoperable tools, namely with “Decision support tool for alternative water sources’ allocation in urban non-potable uses” and “Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse”.

7.5.6 Tool Limitations

The free version is not user-friendly by requiring the use of Windows command-line, by the lack of a graphical interface allowing for the visualization of chlorine concentration profiles along the system and by its limited exporting capability.

7.5.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating safe water reuse through mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution systems, it is intended for use throughout the entire project cycle, from the planning to the application stages.

7.5.8 Key Principles

Diversification: By incorporating reclaimed water into distribution systems, water utilities can diversify their water supply sources. This reduces reliance on traditional freshwater sources, such as rivers and groundwater, which may be vulnerable to depletion or contamination. Diversifying water sources enhances water security and resilience, especially in regions prone to drought or water scarcity.

Ecosystem Preservation: Using reclaimed water for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation, industrial processes, or toilet flushing, reduces the demand for freshwater extraction from natural ecosystems. This helps preserve freshwater ecosystems by maintaining adequate water levels and minimizing habitat degradation caused by excessive water withdrawal. Also, implementing a reclaimed water quality model ensures that reclaimed water meets appropriate standards for its intended use, thereby minimizing the risk of contaminant discharge into receiving water bodies. By preventing pollution from entering rivers, lakes, and streams, reclaimed water distribution systems help protect aquatic ecosystems and the biodiversity they support.

7.5.9 Core Terms

Reclaimed Water Distribution Systems: Reclaimed water distribution systems are networks of pipes, pumps, valves, and other infrastructure designed to transport treated wastewater (reclaimed water) from

treatment plants to end-users for various non-potable uses such as irrigation, industrial processes, and toilet flushing. These systems aim to maximize the reuse of wastewater, conserving freshwater resources and reducing the strain on potable water supplies.

Hydraulic Modelling: Hydraulic modelling is a computational technique used to simulate the behaviour of water flow within hydraulic systems, such as distribution systems. It involves mathematical and computational algorithms to predict the movement, pressure, velocity, and distribution of water under various conditions, including changes in elevation, flow rates, and pipe characteristics.

Water Quality Model: A water quality model is a mathematical representation of the processes that affect the quality of water in a natural or engineered system, such as water distribution systems. These models simulate the interactions of physical, chemical, and biological factors that influence water quality. As key barrier for water microbial stability in distribution systems, as to guarantee a safe application at the point of use, residual chlorine decay is the key parameter to model.

Residual Chlorine: Residual chlorine refers to the concentration of chlorine remaining in water after chlorination or disinfection treatment. Chlorine is commonly used as a disinfectant in water treatment processes to kill or inactivate harmful pathogens, bacteria, and viruses. The residual chlorine level in treated water serves as an indicator of the effectiveness of disinfection and the maintenance of microbial safety during storage and distribution. It is typically measured in milligrams per litre (mg/L) or parts per million (ppm). Controlling residual chlorine levels is important to ensure the continued protection of public health while minimizing the formation of disinfection by-products.

7.5.10 Related Standards

[ISO 20426:2018](#) - Guidelines for risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document aims to serve as technical guidelines for the assessment and management of the health risks associated with pathogens contained in reclaimed water, which are expected to be caused by the use of reclaimed water, and/or by the production, storage, and transportation of reclaimed water. This document is applicable to the use of reclaimed water made from any source water (i.e. raw sanitary sewage; treated municipal wastewater; industrial wastewater; stormwater potentially influenced by sewage) and for non-potable water reuse.

[ISO 20468-1:2018](#) Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems – Part 1: General. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document gives guidelines on performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems. It provides typical parameters of water quality and treatment efficiency that are associated with the performances of treatment technologies. It also includes a comparison of measured and target values and provides treatment technology functional requirements and non-functional requirements.

[ISO 16075-2:2020](#) - Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects - Part2: Development of the project. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document covers the following issues: — guideline for the design of treated wastewater (TWW) irrigation projects intended to prevent public health risks within the population that has been in direct or indirect contact with the TWW or with any product that has come in contact with the TWW; — specifications of the following: i) TWW quality for irrigation purposes; ii) types of crops for TWW irrigated; iii) TWW and crops qualities integration; iv) use of barriers to reduce risks arising from TWW irrigation; v) correlation between the

quality of the TWW, irrigated crops, and the types of barriers that can be used; vi) distance between TWW irrigated areas and residential areas.

7.5.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 16: Step by step guide for Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems.

1. Infrastructural model of the network (data required) implemented in ArcGIS or other format compatible with EPANET open-access software
2. Import the network diagram to EPANET and calibrate the model with water consumption profile data (data required, hydraulic engineering experts)
3. Validate the use of the water quality model (chlorine decay) available or adjust it to the specific water based on lab data (chlorine demand and organic matter & nitrogen content characterization) (data required)
4. Implement the water quality model (MSX) in the EPANET-MSX software
5. Assess the water velocities and age in the network, as well as the chlorine residual in critical points for water safety
6. Manage the network to have a safe water supply, i.e., to have the right chlorine residuals to minimize water contamination and biological regrowth.

The beta-version developed (requiring a payment fee) allows a very comprehensive visualization and user-friendly customization

7.6 Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse

This tool makes expert-knowledge available for risk managers and stakeholders responsible for non-potable water uses, guiding the user through the inherently complex context of public health and environmental risk guidelines and ensuring compatibility with the latest concepts in ISO standardization and EU regulation. Thus, this tool aims at facilitating safe water reuse by providing a potable water uses in the decision steps and by providing an easy to understand and communicate risk assessment framework.

The framework is designed to primarily assist city authorities in two ways in overcoming barriers related to circular economy practice increase: 1) by guiding the hazard exposure scenarios' configuration and the risk analysis for water reuse and 2) by supporting the development of risk management plans for the safe use of reclaimed water as an alternative water source.

The tool outcome is measured by 3 KPIs from the B-WaterSmart Assessment framework⁶ - whose reference values depend on water scarcity, which is expressed by the water exploitation index plus, WEI+; the higher the scarcity, the higher the water reuse must be for a given performance - Compliant reclaimed water [%], Reclaimed water in non-potable uses [%] and Reclaimed water production [%]

Expected positive impacts measured by increased values of the KPIs on, the physical access to water for irrigation, the physical access to water supply for industrial use and the physical access to drinking water supply in public spaces for quality of life. By aiming at facilitating safe use of reclaimed water the tool can

contribute to mitigate the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to its impacts by enhancing water resource resilience and sustainability.

Cost: Partial funding required

7.6.1 Software Requirements

This tool requires the payment of a fee and can run on any computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access requiring an updated internet browser in any operating environment. At an early stage for testing the adequacy/applicability of the tool to the city, its application by LNEC and the UP2030 city will not require the fee payment. The software provider can be assessed at <https://baseform.com/>

7.6.2 Data Requirements

Input data: descriptors of the main features of the urban facility (e.g., public park) that may impact the human and environmental exposure to the hazards present in the reclaimed water; water descriptors relevant for risk assessment (water demand and reclaimed water quality);

Background data: municipal policy/plans, national and European regulations, relevant standards on water reuse and risk assessment;

Additional data: on risk treatment measures.

7.6.3 Expertise Requirements

Human health and environmental risk assessment requires basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse.

Risk management skills are advantageous but not mandatory since LNEC mentoring/support/capacity building is available within UP2030.

7.6.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources skills and competences. Namely, expertise in risk assessment. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.6.5 Tool Use Context

The tool can be used by planners and designers to integrate reclaimed water in urban planning as a water management solution to improve circularity and resilience (e.g. to drought). It is to be used at non-potable water use specific level: a location (e.g., a garden or a park) or an activity (e.g., street cleaning).

Its main objective is to promote water reuse as a safe urban resilience strategy. This is a product of the B-WaterSmart H2020 project (2020-2024) and it may be used individually or in a set of B-WaterSmart complementary and interoperable tools, namely with “Decision support tool for alternative water sources’ allocation in urban non-potable uses” and “Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems”.

7.6.6 Tool Limitations

The beta-version developed (requiring a payment fee) allows a very comprehensive visualization and user-friendly customization. It has no limitations.

7.6.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating safe water reuse through qualifying risk in water reuse locations or activities, it is intended for use throughout the entire project cycle, from the planning to the application stages.

7.6.8 Key Principles

By aiming at facilitating safe use of reclaimed water the tool can contribute to mitigate the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to its impacts by enhancing water resource resilience and sustainability.

Diversification: By incorporating reclaimed water into distribution systems, water utilities can diversify their water supply sources. This reduces reliance on traditional freshwater sources, such as rivers and groundwater, which may be vulnerable to depletion or contamination. Diversifying water sources enhances water security and resilience, especially in regions prone to drought or water scarcity.

Ecosystem Preservation: Using reclaimed water for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation, industrial processes, or toilet flushing, reduces the demand for freshwater extraction from natural ecosystems. This helps preserve freshwater ecosystems by maintaining adequate water levels and minimizing habitat degradation caused by excessive water withdrawal.

Systems Thinking: A special consideration of the interrelations and connections between seemingly separate elements and services of the city or region, to create more holistic approaches towards a water smarter society.

7.6.9 Core Terms

Risk: The likelihood of identified hazards causing harm in a specified timeframe, including the severity of the consequences. [reference: Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse – Reg (EU) 2020/741].

Hazard: A biological, chemical, physical or radiological agent that has the potential to cause harm to people, animals, crops or plants, other terrestrial biota, aquatic biota, soils or the environment in general. [reference: Reg (EU) 2020/741]

Water Reuse Risk Management: The systematic management that consistently ensures that water reuse is safe in a specific context. [reference: Reg (EU) 2020/741]

Risk Assessment: The assessment of risks to the environment and to human and animal health, considering the nature of the identified potential hazards, the duration of the intended uses, the identified environments and populations at risk of exposure to those hazards and the severity of possible effects of the hazards. The risk assessment may be carried out using qualitative or semi-quantitative risk assessment. [reference: Reg (EU) 2020/741]

7.6.10 Related Standards

[ISO 20426:2018](#) - Guidelines for risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document aims to serve as technical guidelines for the assessment and management of the health risks associated with pathogens contained in reclaimed water, which are expected to be caused by the use of reclaimed water, and/or by the production, storage, and transportation of reclaimed water. This document is applicable to the use of

reclaimed water made from any source water (i.e. raw sanitary sewage; treated municipal wastewater; industrial wastewater; stormwater potentially influenced by sewage) and for non-potable water reuse.

[ISO 16075-2:2020](#) - Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects - Part2: Development of the project. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland. This document covers the following issues: 1) a guideline for the design of treated wastewater (TWW) irrigation projects intended to prevent public health risks within the population; 2) specifications including the TWW quality and the use of barriers to reduce risks arising from TWW irrigation.

7.6.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 17: Step by step guide for Risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse.

<p>1. In the menu Configuration, the user is asked to describe the following groups of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Components” organized in 5 subgroups: “Hazards”, “Exposure routes”, “Exposure sites”, “Activities”, and “Population or environment at risk”. The user must fill in the fields “Category” and “Name” of every component. - “Barriers”, including the indication of “Name”, “Expected Log removal value”, “Number of barriers”, and “Reference” of this information. - “Preventive measures”. For each one, the user must fill in the field “Name” of every measure. - “Hazardous events”. The user must fill in the field “Name” of every hazardous event. <p>The data input in the configuration menu provides the necessary information for the risk assessment process, which is organised in the following steps: risk identification, risk analysis and risk treatment.</p>
<p>2. The risk analysis is carried out in the Analysis menu, scenario by scenario. After selecting the demand (i.e., a green area irrigated with reclaimed water), the user describes the scenarios together with the respective risk assessment using the menu “Create scenario”. This menu sequentially presents a set of fields that are filled in with information provided in the "configuration" menu or require rating a of the likelihood of exposure to hazards or the potential damage to the population or environment at risk.</p>
<p>3. The risk analysis is done for every defined exposure scenario, assigning to each scenario a rating for the likelihood of exposure to the hazards, as well as a rating of the harm that might result to the recipient (persons and environment). The levels used for the classification of likelihood and harm are predefined (i.e., not available for configuration by the user).</p>
<p>4. The risk assessment ends with the comparison of the results of the risk analysis with the established criteria to determine whether the residual risk is tolerable, using a risk matrix.</p>

8 Maggioli SpA

For more than 100 years Maggioli SpA has been run as a family company which, for four generations, has made Corporate Social Responsibility a way of doing business. They have a track record of working with a range of diverse institutions (schools, universities, research centres, local and national administrations) whilst planning and supporting initiatives that place them as part of the innovation process. They have experience supporting local and central public administrations, freelancers and companies through a range of technological services, from 'applications for mobile' devices' and 'computerised document storage services' through to offering consultancy and organisational support for public management. They are now expanding into the leading-edge fields of the internet of things, artificial intelligence and smart urbanism.

<https://www.maggioli.com/en-us>

8.1 MIRA Digital Twins Platform

MIRA as a digital twin tool provides cities with the ability to create virtual replicas of urban environments. These replicas allow city planners and officials to simulate various scenarios, optimize infrastructure, and enhance decision-making processes. Digital twins enable efficient urban planning, helping to design better transportation systems, allocate resources effectively, and prepare for emergencies. By integrating real-time data from sensors, they facilitate proactive maintenance of critical infrastructure, extending its lifespan and reducing costs. Furthermore, digital twins foster citizen engagement by providing interactive platforms for residents to explore and contribute to urban development projects. They also support sustainability efforts by analysing environmental data and aiding in the implementation of eco-friendly policies. Overall, digital twin tools offer cities a powerful means to improve efficiency, resilience, and citizen satisfaction in the face of complex urban challenges.

The following innovative aspects can be associated with MIRA:

- Advanced Data Integration and Analytics
- Data ingestion from different sources and owners (not only city authorities but also other third parties)
- Real-time Predictive Capabilities
- Cross-domain Applications: Digital twins can bridge the gap between traditionally isolated domains, such as manufacturing, supply chain, and maintenance, it would represent a significant innovation. This seamless integration would lead to a holistic view of operations and enable better decision-making across the organization.
- Virtual Simulation and Scenario Planning
- User-friendly Interface and Accessibility
- Security and Privacy Measures

Cost: No funding required

8.1.1 Software Requirements

MIRA is a cloud-based platform, directly accessible through a web browser. No extra software is required for the end user. Integration with various data sources may require documented APIs or predefined files for import (json, csv etc).

8.1.2 Data Requirements

In principle MIRA integrates two types of data:

Sensor data (any type of sensor, camera or devices that send information about a particular issue)

Services (more complicated set of data, alerts, notifications and anything that has to be aggregated and reused in a dashboard for monitoring purposes, or for processed in the context of another service).

Depending on the context, we can integrate different information. For instance, in a mobility case we can integrate data from:

- Cameras (to identify mobility congestion rates or patterns of congestion)
- Street lighting
- Mobility service operator solutions
- Energy demand and other related info/services
- Other.

For energy purposes (buildings) MIRA can integrate also various data:

- From sensors (temperature, occupancy, HVAC operation, etc.)
- BIM Models
- Energy management solution data

If a city wants to keep track of a sustainability index in different areas, then MIRA can aggregate information from:

- Sensors (Noise, CO2, etc.)
- Possible data about occupancy and other operations of the area MIRA can be used to monitor the performance of those sensors, and create a module for sustainability where we can associate sustainability metrics with urban operations, thus identifying needs for improvements and interventions.

In all the above case, MIRA aggregates them and on top of the modelled digital twin can run different services (or integrate third party services) such as:

- Simulation (forecasting of energy demand, predict mobility, what-if scenarios for green interventions)
- Or any other applicable service developed by UP2030 or service used by the pilots

The main advantage of MIRA is the aggregation of the different information sources to different topologies and execute what-if scenarios for area interventions.

8.1.3 Expertise Requirements

No specific need from local authorities, just some training on the use of the tool.

8.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Interoperability issues may arise due to the need to integrate diverse data sources and systems. Resistance to change within organizations and bureaucratic hurdles can slow down the adoption process. Lastly, lack of awareness or understanding of the benefits of digital twins may lead to scepticism among stakeholders. Overcoming these barriers requires addressing interoperability issues early in the process, promoting awareness and education and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.

8.1.5 Tool Use Context

MIRA allows for creating virtual replicas of urban environments, including buildings, infrastructure, and services. It's employed to optimize urban planning, infrastructure management, and citizen engagement. City planners utilize digital twins to simulate various development scenarios, analyse transportation systems, and optimize resource allocation. These tools aid in proactive maintenance of critical infrastructure, monitoring energy consumption, water usage, and waste management. Moreover, digital twins enhance emergency preparedness by simulating disaster scenarios and testing response strategies.

Additionally, digital twins support sustainability efforts by analysing environmental data and facilitating the implementation of eco-friendly policies. Overall, in the context of a city, digital twin tools are invaluable for data-driven decision-making, improving efficiency, resilience, and citizen satisfaction in urban development and management.

8.1.6 Tool Limitations

For the scope of the pilots and the current state of the tool, MIRA can be used as a visualization and integration platform to monitor, aggregate and analyse information received from sensors or integrated from existing data sources a city may possess. Simulation of what-if scenarios requires modelling of each use case scenario separately (i.e. inputs-algorithm-outputs) which can be generalized but in some cases are pilot-specific and would be difficult to replicate them. Integration of available data and services requires the sources of information to be fully documented. Digital twins face challenges such as data accuracy, scalability, and integration complexity. Real-time updates, data accuracy, privacy concerns, cost barriers and usability can also pose as limitations (depending on the case in a smart city DT); however, MIRA considers data governance principles on how and to whom data is shared among stakeholders.

8.1.7 City Journey

MIRA could be used at various stages of a city's journey, from initial planning to ongoing management. It's crucial during urban development for simulating different scenarios, optimizing infrastructure, and engaging citizens. In operation, it aids in monitoring and managing resources efficiently, predicting maintenance needs, and enhancing emergency preparedness. Continuously, it helps in adapting to evolving needs and challenges, ensuring sustainability and resilience. Overall, digital twin tools are most effective when integrated throughout the city's lifecycle, supporting data-driven decision-making, efficiency, and citizen satisfaction from planning to ongoing management.

The only prerequisite is that the city must already have the required data available, either through deploying sensors and IoT devices, conducting studies or strategic plans etc.

8.1.8 Key Principles

MIRA is a digital twin tool which can be of aid in various fields like urban planning, infrastructure management, citizen engagement, energy consumption, water usage, waste management, resource allocation optimization, mobility and more. It is a horizontal tool that can foster a lot of different vertical sectors providing the means to analyse, aggregate and visualize raw data to enable informed decision making. The key principles related to the pilots can be summarized as follows:

Create Your Own Ecosystems: Monitor collaborations at city ecosystem level along with data generated from different owners and in line with agreements and access control principles in data sharing (in line with IDS specifications)

Services Integration: Able to integrate services on top of DT such as simulation, analytics, optimization, third party services and city-custom made services based on their particularities/ needs.

8.1.9 Core Terms

Data Visualization: Data visualization in digital twins involves presenting real-time and/or historical data in a graphical format, aiding users in understanding complex information about physical assets or systems. It enhances decision-making by providing insights into performance, trends, and anomalies, facilitating proactive management and optimization of resources.

Data Aggregation and KPI Calculation: Data aggregation in digital twins involves gathering and consolidating data from various sources to create a comprehensive view of a system or asset. KPI calculation analyses this data to assess performance, identify trends, and measure against predefined benchmarks, aiding in decision-making and optimization efforts.

8.1.10 Related Standards

As a horizontal tool that can foster a lot of different vertical sectors providing the means to analyse, aggregate and visualize raw data to enable informed decision making. Thus, the standards of each vertical sector apply, depending on the area of interest.

8.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 18: Step by step guide for MIRA Digital Twins Platform.

<p>1. Understand the assets/ networks to be modelled. This step involves discussion with key stakeholders and city representatives to define the vertical sector(s) of interest, the area or point of interest and the available data.</p>
<p>2. Model the assets/ networks as Digital Twins (along with their interconnections). In this step, using the information gathered in the previous step, we examine what functionalities of MIRA can be used and whether any additional development is required (if yes, the extra functionalities are developed). Then the assets / points/ areas / networks defined in step 1 are modelled within MIRA.</p>
<p>3. Integrate information source(s). In this step all the available data for the aforementioned assets, points, areas or networks are connected with the modelled assets. If connectors are required in order to receive real-time information that is available through sensors or other IoT devices, then these connectors are also developed.</p>

4. Integrate existing services or create new on top of each digital twin. In this final step we connect existing services, platforms or create new services on the defined assets or networks. In this step we also produce the required visualizations for the end user, aggregating the required data and producing the predefined KPI values

9 Mapping for Change

Mapping for Change works to provide benefit to individuals and communities from disadvantaged or marginalised groups, along with the organisations and networks that support those communities, where the goal is to create positive sustainable transformations in their environment. They are experts in the use of Geographical Information Systems, applying it to meet client needs. They also support individuals from the aforementioned groups to gain access to higher education at University College London, to study fields connected with our work.

<https://mappingforchange.org.uk/>

9.1 Community Maps and GeoKey

An online interactive mapping platform that enables the collection and visualization of crowdsourced data offers several advantages:

- **Rich and Diverse Data:** Crowdsourcing allows for the collection of a wide range of data points from a large number of contributors. This results in a diverse and rich dataset that can provide comprehensive insights and perspectives.
- **Real-Time Updates:** With crowdsourced data, the platform can provide real-time updates as users contribute new information. This enables users to stay informed about the latest developments and changes in the mapped areas.
- **Rapid Data Collection:** Crowdsourcing allows for the collection of data at a much faster pace compared to traditional methods. By leveraging a large number of users, the platform can rapidly gather and process information, making it ideal for time-sensitive situations such as disaster response or public health emergencies.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Crowdsourcing data can be a cost-effective approach compared to conducting extensive field surveys or hiring specialized data collection teams. By utilizing the collective effort of volunteers or interested individuals, the platform can gather data without significant financial investments.
- **Data Visualization and Analysis:** Interactive maps and visualizations provide a user-friendly and intuitive way to explore and analyse data. Users can identify patterns, trends, and correlations through visual representations, enabling them to make informed decisions or gain valuable insights.
- **Decision-Making Support:** The availability of crowdsourced data and visualizations can aid decision-makers in various fields. Governments, organizations, and researchers can utilize the platform to understand community needs, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions based on reliable data. This data can also be integrated or overlaid with existing datasets, plans and projects to support the decision-making process.

Overall, an online interactive mapping platform that leverages crowdsourced data provides a valuable resource for gathering, visualizing, and utilizing information. It promotes collaboration, community

engagement, and informed decision-making while harnessing the power of collective knowledge and contributions.

Cost: No funding required

9.1.1 [Software Requirements](#)

Community Maps and GeoKey are web-based platforms (web-apps) for participatory mapping. GeoKey provides the server-side infrastructure to receive, store and disseminate geographic data collected by citizens via an open web API. The backend infrastructure provided by GeoKey enables Governments, organizations, researchers, or other relevant bodies to set-up projects, manage access to data and to store and validate data without any technical or specialized know-how required. Community Maps provides a client-side application to collect, manage, visualise, and analyse the data stored in GeoKey through a graphic user interface. This is the interface with which the public interacts. These applications, when deployed together, provide an out-of-the-box solution which has been delivered for different contexts and use cases over the past nine years as a SaaS model by Mapping for Change.

9.1.2 [Data Requirements](#)

Table 19: Data Requirements for Community Maps and GeoKey.

<p>The following data types are supported:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● text ● number ● single lookup ● multiple lookup ● date ● time
<p>The following file types for upload to an individual map contribution are supported:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PNG ● JPEG ● MP4 ● MKV ● PDF ● MP3
<p>The following file types for data import to create new categories and map contributions or add to existing categories to generate new contributions are supported:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GeoJSON ● CSV ● KML

9.1.3 [Expertise Requirements](#)

No background - it is designed to be easy to use with minimal training (2hrs)

No GIS skills or specific technical know-how are required to set up new mapping projects.

9.1.4 [Potential Barriers to Use](#)

The tool aims to support municipalities to engage stakeholders in understanding their needs, codeveloping their vision, interventions and eliciting feedback to support the evaluation of any actions. For that, municipalities need to be aware of the potential usefulness of the solution at an early stage if their engagement activities.

9.1.5 [Tool Use Context](#)

The tool is designed to be flexible and adaptable for use in a variety of contexts where spatial data collection and visualization can benefit from the added value of engaging the public, to both contribute to and review spatial data, to support decision making processes. A brief introduction to the community maps

platform can be found and a user guide to the interface can be viewed on the 'Mapping for Change' YouTube channel.

9.1.6 [Tool Limitations](#)

The applications are web-apps and as such require an internet connection to be utilized. The need for an internet connection make exclude some groups and factors such as digital literacy also need to be considered.

9.1.7 [City Journey](#)

These tools can be used throughout a cities project cycle, from the identification of needs and barriers to reaching their climate neutrality goals, through to monitoring and assessing the impact of policies and interventions.

9.1.8 [Key Principles](#)

Community Engagement: An interactive mapping platform encourages community engagement and participation. It empowers individuals to contribute to their local communities, share their experiences, and collaborate with others. This sense of involvement can foster a stronger community bond and a collective effort towards shared goals.

Flexibility and Adaptability: The platform can be adapted to various use cases and domains. It can accommodate different types of data, such as environmental data, social data, transportation data, or cultural data. The flexibility of the platform allows it to address a wide range of challenges and applications.

Local Knowledge and Expertise: Crowdsourced data often captures local knowledge and expertise that may not be easily accessible through other means. Individuals living in specific areas can contribute valuable insights, observations, and recommendations that enhance the overall accuracy and relevance of the data.

9.1.9 [Core Terms](#)

Crowdsourcing: The idea of using the power of a crowd to collect data that is too vast, heterogeneous, or expensive to be collected by other means.

Volunteered geographic information (VGI): This kind of data is collected by citizens acting as sensors to gather information about the world around them. The citizens then feed this information into a centralized GIS database, often employing a user interface that has been simplified to the degree that specialized training is not required.

Participatory Mapping: Also referred to as 'community mapping', is based on the premise that local inhabitants hold accurate knowledge of their local environments which can be expressed in maps which are easily understandable.

9.1.10 [Related Standards](#)

No specific standards are required.

9.1.11 [Step-by-Step Guide](#)

Table 20: Step by step guide for Community Maps and GeoKey.

1. The first step is to establish the purpose of the map. Consider what information you would like to collect on the map and what information you would like to display from existing sources, for example current cycle lanes. The data you wish to collect, i.e. by a person adding a pin, shape or line on the map, may be to fill in some specific gaps in knowledge, for example un-used buildings or more general information such as public opinions of the local greenspaces. Workshops and pop-up events with stakeholders can be useful to understand the priorities for data collection from different perspectives.

2. The second step is to agree on the geographical area of focus, although this can be edited at a later stage if the scale of the neighbourhood changes

3. The third step is to gather and clean all the existing datasets to display on the map - this can be imported to the platform as different layers where the coordinate data is available at the right scale. Organise the data like any other database, with standardised fields for the information

4. The fourth step is to build the map layers to gather the new data sets. It is important not to make the map too complex that the general public would be off-put or confused but equally it needs to be useful and usable. Each layer of data can have different fields with which to gather further detail for each point added to the map. Consider what is essential information and what would be 'nice to have'

5. Once built, the map should be tested with a focus group or selected individuals to identify any areas of confusion, lack of clarity or gaps in data. These can become ambassadors for the map at a later stage for dissemination

6. After the testing phase, it needs to be decided who can view the map and who can contribute to it (from completely open to the public to limited to specified individuals) and whether moderation or a log-in is required.

7. A core team should take responsibility for maintaining and moderating the map. The members will receive training on how to edit and moderate the map content and structure and on how to export the data from the map for analysis

8. Once the map is published it needs to be shared in order for people to be able to contribute. This may be done through different engagement activities; online through social networks and via existing communication channels of the map ambassadors

10 TSPA

TSPA (Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture) is an international urban planning and design firm that develops sustainable urban systems for a changing world. They have delivered projects ranging from regional development to urban planning - from neighbourhood design to place-making. Their team is composed of talented planners, designers, urbanists, data, and communication experts from nine countries. Besides their work with German cities, TSPA have realised projects on four continents, drawing upon global experience to find innovative solutions for each context, be it abroad or at home.

<https://tspa.eu/en>

10.1 Spatial Analysis tool - Data Driven Geospatial Analysis

The Tool aims at interpreting complex spatial systems through advanced spatial analysis and remote sensing methods, which supports decision making by simplifying and overlaying spatial systems to support decision making. The Spatial Analysis tool allows the evaluation and visualization of various diverse but interlinked systems - such as but not limited to built environment, natural environment, socio-economic, demographic and urban systems - and works to provide the results in an easy-to-understand fashion.

This tool illustrates the impact of current trends across temporal (short-term, intermediate, long-term) and spatial dimensions across scales to evaluate the suggested planning and design options with the goal of achieving high level targets and goals efficiently and effectively.

Cost: Funding required

10.1.1 Software Requirements

The Spatial Analysis tool is offered as a service that adapts to the city's needs, the software requirement is related to the type of analysis and results that a city is aiming for. The results can be in static image formats such as maps, or interactive maps using online platforms, the results also include spatial and non-spatial data that require specialized software to view and operate e.g. Microsoft Excel/Geographic information systems (GIS) if necessary.

The tool is operated using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and works to integrate various methods and approaches with in-house expertise to leverage the power of spatial analysis and bring holistic tailor-made solutions to the city with minimal software and technical skills requirements.

10.1.2 Data Requirements

The Spatial analysis tool leverages Deep-learning approaches to extract spatial data from satellite and aerial imagery to compensate for possible lack of data. However, geospatial open-source and governmental data is a necessary starting component to operate this tool, spatial data may include:

- Vector spatial data (e.g. shapefile)
- Raster and satellite imagery (e.g. GeoTIF)
- Spatialized CSV data
- Social media data scraping

- CAD or architectural data (e.g. dwg)

The methodology relies on spatial data that is compatible with GIS software such as ArcGIS or QGIS and is accepted by EU standards. The examples of the data format include but are not limited to: Geography Markup Language, GeoJSON, Keyhole Mark-up Language, GeotIF, and Network Common Data Form, Shapefile.

10.1.3 Expertise Requirements

A combination of technical and analytical competencies is required to operate and develop the spatial analysis tool, as well as a design-oriented approach and a higher education in the fields of urban planning and urban design.

To view and work with the results of the Spatial Analysis Tool, basic understanding of data analysis, and urban planning principles is required.

10.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Lack of data: Not having adequate spatial data will have a negative impact on the analysis and results of the tool.

Lack of expertise: The method demands knowledge as an urban planner and advanced GIS abilities. Within the UP2030 project there will be no training for GIS/planning certificates, but the overall methods can be taught and transferred in their holistic and cross-cutting approach. In addition, the shortage in digital skills among city representatives and the lack of up to date and comprehensive datasets may limit the solution.

10.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is designed to answer spatial questions through advanced analysis and visualization approaches. The Spatial Analysis tool is designed for flexibility and accuracy, where it aims to adapt to different context and analytical tasks, and it has the capacities to integrate and feed from and to other quantitative tools, such as the Parametric Design tool. The tool's general scope allows it to be used in various scenarios where the client/city officials would like to answer questions related to the dynamics and performance of their city.

10.1.6 Tool Limitations

Accuracy considerations: The accuracy of the results is directly related to the accuracy of the data, if the input data is missing or inaccurate, this will have a direct negative influence on the results.

Micro scale details limitations: The Spatial Analysis tool is built inside a GIS environment which is effective between the urban and regional scales, for micro scale modelling and analysis, other digital environments are better suited to address the higher level of spatial resolution, such as the Parametric Design tool using Rhino + Grasshopper and CAD software.

10.1.7 City Journey

The Spatial Analysis tool is flexible and can be used, implemented, and customized at any stage of the city's journey. It largely depends on the scope of the project. If, for example, a city is aiming to develop an infill project – using the spatial analysis tool for gaining a deeper understanding of the contextual challenges which affect the project would be critical in the early stages. Whereas it is also possible to use the tool to analyse the impact of a given project in certain dimensions after its completion. In such a case the tool would be highly valuable in its later stage implementation.

10.1.8 Key Principles

Spatial Data Extraction: The Deep learning component of the Spatial Analysis tool aims to extract spatial data for cities needs, for example, counting the number of trees in a given area or Generating building footprints.

Spatial Analysis: to visualize, understand, and interpret data relationships and patterns across geographic spaces, informing decisions on land use, infrastructure development, and environmental management.

Data-driven Decision Making: Through specialized analysis and visualization approaches, the tool aims to guide decision making processes, where the results are tailored to answer spatial questions with reliable and accurate information.

10.1.9 Core Terms

Spatial Data: Information about the positions and shapes of objects and their distribution across geographic spaces.

Analysis Methods: Techniques used to examine, manipulate, and interpret spatial data to reveal patterns, trends, and relationships.

Spatial Modelling: The process of representing real-world phenomena within a spatial context to predict and analyse patterns and interactions.

Result Data: The outcome of spatial analyses, often in the form of processed information or insights derived from spatial data.

Visualizations: Graphical representations of spatial data designed to make complex information more understandable and accessible.

Interactive Maps: Dynamic maps that allow users to manipulate view settings, explore data layers, and retrieve detailed information through interaction.

Static Maps: Fixed representations of spatial data, offering a snapshot of geographical information at a specified range of or point in time.

Recommendations: Advised actions or strategies derived from the analysis of spatial data, aimed at informed decision-making in urban planning.

10.1.10 Related Standards

Data Protection and Privacy Standards: Standards such as [GDPR](#) in the EU dictate how user data will be handled and protected. Data protection is essential for the Spatial Analysis tool to store sensitive urban data such as demographics, or average income.

OGC Standards: [Open Geospatial Consortium standards](#), such as the GML, and shapefiles are important to ensure interoperability of Geospatial data.

10.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Table 21: Step by step guide for Spatial Analysis tool - Data Driven Geospatial Analysis.

1. Data collection: Spatial data are collected from different sources and organised into a structured dataset that can be updated in real time. The decision making on which data to analyse requires advanced knowledge in local policy objectives and urban planning processes.
2. Data driven analysis: Data are harmonised, processed and classified using analytic frameworks and GIS based tools to identify opportunities and threats. Intermediate to advanced GIS skills are required for this step
3. Trend analysis: Projections are developed to evaluate the impact of current trends. GIS-based tools may be used depending on the context and available data.
4. Visualization and results: The last step in this approach is to present the analysis and modelling results in a relevant way. This may be statically visualized maps, focusing on a single or multiple results, interactive maps that allow the user to explore the resulting patterns dynamically. And the output data, which can be used for further analysis and documentation

10.2 Parametric Design Tool

Conventional urban design methods usually follow a relatively linear pattern, where designs and concepts are explored through initial phases with little analysis and data-driven approaches being involved. The parametric approach aims to expand the exploration of possible designs in a systematic and tailored approach, focusing on the targets of the project, and examining the relationship of factors and how they impact each other e.g. energy efficiency, spatial configuration, urban morphology, distribution of services, etc. This design approach allows for better and more insightful discussions and stakeholder involvement through the rapid generation and exploration of multiple design scenarios, while providing quantitative forecasts on the impact, advantages, and challenges of the design scenarios. A city should consider this tool when aiming for urban designs, especially when working with other analytical tools since this could allow for synchronizing outputs and integrating into multiple urban design proposals.

This tool provides an urban design approach that aims to computationally integrate multiple factors and criteria in designing urban spaces. This facilitates the exploration of multiple design scenarios, spatial configurations, and possible futures for the pilot/development area. The tool's approach informs decision making through systematic exploration of urban design factors and their impact. The tool has been tested and implemented by TSPA in previous projects, however, the tool is not one size fit all, and will be tailored, adapted, and redeveloped to meet the pilot/city needs.

Cost: Funding required

10.2.1 Software Requirements

Since the parametric design tool is tailored to the need of each city, the tool is offered as a service, with no software/technical knowledge requirements. The tool will be developed in house through feedback loops with the cities.

10.2.2 [Data Requirements](#)

To operate and develop the tool optimally, geospatial data is necessary, this includes spatial data such as building footprints, land-use, demographic data, topography and Digital Elevation Models to name a few. If such data is unavailable or lacking, TSPA's spatial analysis tool can be deployed to extract spatial data and information to assist the development of the Parametric Design Tool.

10.2.3 [Expertise Requirements](#)

As the tool is offered as a service, no specific expertise is required. As mentioned, the tool requires only feedback and alignment meeting to ensure effective tailoring to the city's needs.

10.2.4 [Potential Barriers to Use](#)

Lack of data: While the spatial analysis tool provides a viable source of data in case of data scarcity, some data such as demographics and accurate land use can only be provided from the city, lacking this data would influence the development and accuracy of the parametric design tool.

Underdeveloped visions: The vision of the target area guides the customization and tailoring of the parametric design tool, lacking a vision or clear targets could negatively influence effective development and implementation of the parametric design tool.

Technical challenges: The process of developing the parametric design tool is highly complex. Modelling the systematic relationship between design factors in the parametric design environment is heavily time intensive and can run into a wide range of development bugs and other barriers.

10.2.5 [Tool Use Context](#)

The parametric design tool is developed for urban design projects, where the client/city are interested in exploring multiple design scenarios to meet certain goals/objectives and make data-driven and informed decisions on the design and planning choices.

10.2.6 [Tool Limitations](#)

While the customization and tailoring process of the tool ensures adequate and effective implementation for individual cities, this requires intensive time and effort for this development. Though the tool aims to provide a comprehensive approach for urban design, modelling and relating urban design factors is complicated, and might have some limitations in certain cases.

10.2.7 [City Journey](#)

It is optimal to use the parametric design tool during or soon after the visioning phase. The tool can be used in part to facilitate the visioning process – if it is integrated early enough. Otherwise, it can be used directly after the visioning process to develop conceptual designs.

10.2.8 [Key Principles](#)

Informed Decision Making: The analytical and iterative nature of the tool aims and allows for exploring multiple design scenarios and their impact to understand and optimize design and planning decisions.

Climate Neutrality: At its core, the tool aims to integrate principles of energy efficiency, and climate adaptability, and understanding the trade-offs of related choices.

10.2.9 Core Terms

Factors: factors are high level objectives, goals, or concepts that the new development aims to implement/achieve. The factors are identified through feedback discussions with the city, literature research, and best practices.

Parameters: parameters are the quantitative/numeric breakdowns of factors. For example, Floor Area Ratio, tree density, solar irradiation, etc.

Scenarios: are the result of qualitative summing of the factors, typically a scenario matrix consists of two dimensions and four quadrants that explore the possible futures for the pilot development, scenarios are theoretical concepts that aim to explore the characteristics of the new development, and are used as an alignment and communication tool with the city and stakeholders

Design Scenarios: design scenarios are spatial plans and configurations / urban design proposals that explore detailed urban design options for the development area, the design scenarios are the main output of the parametric design tool, and are directly controlled by parameters, and heavily guided by the factors and the scenarios.

10.2.10 Related Standards

Data Protection and Privacy Standards: Standards such as [GRPR](#) in the EU dictate how user data will be handled and protected. Data protection is essential for the Parametric Design tool to store sensitive urban data, and possible design proposals.

10.2.11 Step-by-Step Guide

Since the parametric design tool is provided as a service, TSPA will handle the technical development of the tool, but to ensure an effective implementation a series of feedback and alignment talks / workshops are necessary to be conducted with the clients and stakeholders, this includes:

- Definition of a vision statement for the pilot site
- Factors identifications and review
- Stakeholder engagement workshops on scenarios
- Feedback loops during the parametric development
- Evaluation and iteration of the design scenarios

11 UCCRN

The Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN) is a global consortium of over 1,200 individuals from over 150 cities dedicated to the analysis of climate change mitigation and adaptation from an urban perspective. UCCRN members are scholars and experts from universities and research organizations around the world. They span a broad range of expertise including climate scientists; urban heat island and air quality experts; climate change impact scientists; social scientists, including economists, political scientists, and sociologists; and urban designers and planners.

<https://uccrn.ei.columbia.edu/about-us>

11.1 UDCW Simulation Toolkit

Climate resilient development in cities requires integration of mitigation and adaptation measures across spatial scales. The UDCW simulation toolkit consists in set of IT tools (GIS and 3d Modelling Algorithm Aided Design tools) for heat waves and flood hazard/impact modelling considering urban microclimate effect (morphology, land use and cover, building features, etc.), including user guidance. It allows the user to perform analyses at city (2D) and neighbourhood (3d) scales based on climate projection information.

Testing of the effectiveness of alternative strategies at a conceptual stage of the plan/project - through a set of interoperable tools embedded into common planning and design software (GIS and 3D modelling tools) which are integrated with simulation modules supporting the assessment of climate benefits from different planning and design strategies at different scales through few input parameters (climate data, urban morphology, land cover, construction typologies, etc.) - is also possible.

Cost: No funding required

11.1.1 Software Requirements

Any GIS software tool (only for input data collection to be transferred as .shp or .gpkg files).

The UDCW Simulation Toolkit is an on-demand service-based tool, and users can deliver city plans and architectural drawing through any kind of software. The recommended software are Q-GIS for the 2D city plans and Rhinoceros (McNeel) for 3D models. Detailed user guides providing tips to provide simple drawings and models based on data requirement taxonomy are provided, including video tutorials.

11.1.2 Data Requirements

End users are required to transfer to UCCRN experts a series of GIS files (shp, geopackage) including all the input data needed to run the simulation model, according to the taxonomy and attributes listed in UCCRN's data table (See: Section 12: Appendix).

The tools allow to introduce as input specific climate change projections, based on RCPs/SSPs for different future timeframes. The data include both annual averages (targeting e.g. building energy consumption) and extreme events (heat waves and extreme precipitation). The toolkit allows to manage different types of data in the same working environment, streamlining both the design process and the assessment of climate-resilient development strategies, delivering the following output based on specific planning and design solutions.

Thermal comfort analysis

- Mean Radiant Temperature [°C]
- Universal Thermal Climate Index [°C]
- Indoor Predicted Mean Vote
- Hospitalization costs due to heatwaves [€]
- Mortality rate increase [%] (beta)

Flood analysis

- Run-off [-]
- Flood probability index [-]
- Building damage (structure/content) [€]
- Road infrastructure damage (cleaning/repairing) [€]

Energy analysis

- Building Energy Use Intensity [kWh/m²y]
- Renewable energy production potential [kWh/y]

Carbon analysis

- Carbon Footprint of Building Materials [tCO₂/y]
- Carbon storage potential from vegetation [tCO₂/y]

11.1.3 Expertise Requirements

UDCW simulation tools are particularly specialised computational tools. For this reason, their standalone use requires an adequate technical and IT background to be used correctly. Basic knowledge of GIS software to handle the data collection and transfer is also required.

11.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

To reduce barriers that could prevent this tool being used, the tools are offered as a service, only requiring users to prepare the files within GIS software environment, based on a guide provided by UCCRN. UDCW simulations are generally provided as a service by UCCRN EU team, based on specific end-user requirements and user-tailored workflows. However, a lack of the above expertise could prevent the tools from being correctly utilised.

11.1.5 Tool Use Context

The scope of the tool is to provide multi-scale and urban planning and design guidance from strategic/conceptual level, to master planning and neighbourhood scale design. Supported by specific IT tools, GIS and 3D Algorithm Aided Design (AAD), the UDCW Simulation Toolkit provides a fully quantitative and spatialized analysis of climate benefits of planning/design scenario in relation to climate projections downscaled to the urban climate.

The tool provides support for decision-making processes to consider urban climate design principles in city planning, urban and building/open space design and perform robust climate hazard/impact and mitigation/adaptation assessments based on IPCC AR6 and EU Taxonomy/DNSH approaches.

GIS and 3D modelling tools are widely used by designers and planners. Moreover, the implementation of AAD tools allows for an effective and rapid interaction among the software environments, fostering the multi-scale approach proposed. For this reason, the tool is specifically intended to be used by technical planning departments in cities and planning/design practitioners.

11.1.6 Tool Limitations

The toolkit includes a set of climate projections, information and data about temperature and precipitation, including annual averages (through Energy Plus Weather - EPW files, globally) and extreme events (only for EU cities). Limitations might be related in the availability of EPW files for the city. Both annual averages and extreme events data can be provided by users if available.

11.1.7 City Journey

The models included in the UDCW Simulation Toolkit are based on the elaboration of climate projections downscaled to include urban microclimate conditions and simulate the impacts of heat waves on population (mortality rate increase, hospitalization, including economic direct and indirect impacts) and the effect of seasonal temperature trends variation on energy demand for building heating/cooling, and impacts of floods on buildings and open spaces (direct and indirect damage to structure and content).

The tools can measure the climate benefits in terms of adaptation and mitigation measures through fully quantitative indicators, also including assessments of social, economic and environmental co-benefits associated to climate resilient development strategies.

The UDCW Simulation Toolkit can be used throughout the entire project cycle, but it is particularly recommended at the strategic city planning level and the early conceptual stages of an urban/building design project, to make sure that targeted decarbonization and climate adaptation goals are measured through robust quantitative indicators.

11.1.8 Key Principles

Multi-Scale Approach: UDCW Simulation toolkit is aimed at providing an integrated multi-scale approach (city/neighbourhood/building-open spaces) to urban transformation, in which key performance indicators related to carbon neutrality and climate adaptation are quantified concurrently for each proposed planning and design scenario.

11.1.9 Core Terms

Land Use: occupation of urban surface (built-up or open space), including main building typologies (e.g. residential, commercial, industrial, etc.) and land cover category (natural, artificial). Contributes to the definition of key parameters related to energy uses

Land Cover: surface materials (natural or artificial) employed (e.g. agricultural, asphalt road, paved area, etc.). Contributes to the definition of main heat (e.g. emissivity, evapotranspiration) and flood (e.g. run-off) parameters

Mean Radiant Temperature (T_{mrt}): uniform temperature of an imaginary enclosure in which the radiant heat transfer from the human body equals the radiant heat transfer in the actual non-uniform enclosure (ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, 2004). Used as key heat hazard indicator, as a proxy of Urban Heat Island conditions.

Mortality Rate Increase: potential mortality increase during a specific heat wave period, depending on population age groups. Used as key outdoor heat impact indicator (often only applicable at city scale, strongly depending on local health statistics available).

Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI): parameter describing the synergistic heat exchanges between the thermal environment and the human body, namely its energy budget, physiology and clothing. Used as key outdoor heat impact indicator to assess hospitalization costs related to heat waves.

Indoor Predicted Mean Vote (PMV): expected mean response of a large group of people in an indoor environment on a 7-point thermal sensation scale, from +3 (hot) to -3 (cold), where 0 is neutral (the metric is designed for fully mechanically ventilated buildings, in accordance with ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55). Used as key indoor heat impact indicator to assess hospitalization costs related to heat waves.

Flood Probability Index: synthetic parameter that includes the main urban features contributing to accumulation of surface water (e.g. surface run-off, relative altimetry in a urban watershed, density of run-off streams in the area, etc.). Used as key pluvial flood hazard indicator.

Building Energy Use Intensity: expresses a building's energy use as a function of its size, functional program (e.g. residential, office, etc) and characteristics of building envelope and HVAC systems. Used to calculate annual building energy consumption.

Renewable Energy Production Potential: indicates the potential of generating energy from roofs or urban canopy surfaces using photovoltaics. It takes into account the geomorphology of the site and the urban morphology, considering casted shadows and calculating the relative incident solar radiation on the target surfaces for all year and the potential conversion into electricity depending on PV systems efficiency and specific design constraints (e.g. heritage protected buildings, nature protected areas, etc.).

Carbon Footprint of Building Materials: embodied carbon of construction materials along the life-cycle (cradle to cradle), considering main structural systems employed (reinforced concrete, steel, timber) and recurring envelope systems (e.g. building blocks, bricks, lightweight façade systems, etc.)

Carbon Storage Potential from Vegetation: potential storage of CO₂ of vegetation, depending on specific species biomass along the plant's lifecycle

11.1.10 Related Standards

[DNSH](#) assessment protocols

[ISO 14091:2021](#) - Adaptation to climate change: This document gives guidelines for assessing the risks related to the potential impacts of climate change. It describes how to understand vulnerability and how to develop and implement a sound risk assessment in the context of climate change. It can be used for assessing both present and future climate change risks.

[ISO/TR 6030:2022](#) - Disaster risk reduction: This document identifies existing global smart community infrastructures that enhance disaster risk reduction, the key purposes served by these global examples, gaps in coverage, and the need for standardization activities, which establishes the basis for the next steps for standardization. This document is intended to be a basis for the future standardization of smart community infrastructures for disaster risk reduction through the identification of areas for potential standardization. This includes, but is not limited to, infrastructures related to energy, waste and water, transportation, information and communication technologies (ICT), and the general built environment.

[ISO 52120-1:2021](#) - Energy performance of buildings: This document specifies: A structured list of control, building automation and technical building management functions which contribute to the energy performance of buildings; functions have been categorized and structured according to building disciplines and building automation and control (BAC); a method to define minimum requirements or any specification regarding the control, building automation and technical building management functions contributing to energy efficiency of a building to be implemented in building of different complexities; a factor-based method to get a first estimation of the effect of these functions on typical buildings types and use profiles; detailed methods to assess the effect of these functions on a given building.

[ISO 20887, 2020](#). Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Design for disassembly and adaptability: This document provides an overview of design for disassembly and adaptability (DfD/A) principles and potential strategies for integrating these principles into the design process. This document provides information for owners, architects, engineers, and product designers and manufacturers to assist in their understanding of potential DfD/A options and considerations, and for other parties who are responsible for financing, regulating, constructing, transforming, deconstructing, or demolishing construction works.

11.1.11 [Step-by-Step Guide](#)

Table 22: Step by step guide for UDCW Simulation Toolkit.

1. Climate characterization (data provided by UCCRN - e.g. UCCRN data, EuroCordex, EPW - Energy Plus Weather file - or by users if available: climate projections including seasonal averages and extreme events; skills needed: none; actors to be involved: local climate data providers)
2. Urban context characterization (data collection from users: see 3. “Data requirements”; skills needed: GIS basic expertise; actors to be involved: technical planning departments of the city, planning and design consultants)
3. Buildings and population parameters attribution using GIS (urban scale) and Grasshopper (neighbourhood scale) (data collection from users: see 3. “Data requirements”; skills needed: GIS basic expertise; actors to be involved: technical planning departments of the city, planning and design consultants)
4. Simulation run (provided as a service; skills needed: none)

11.2 [UDCW Methodology](#)

UCCRN Urban Design Climate Workshops (UDCWs) aim to integrate and scale-up climate change mitigation and adaptation in cities through knowledge sharing, collaboration, and action planning. Innovative aspects of the UDCW methodology can be recognized in:

1. Provision of a set of designer/planner friendly interoperable tools that are able to assess the climate benefits of different planning and design strategies at different scales both in terms of comfort quantitative indicators and quanti/qualitative co-benefits indicators starting from few input parameters (urban morphology, climate data, land uses, etc.);

2. Understanding of the relation between socio-spatial justice and climate justice providing tools that can spatialize community needs that are often not directly climate related, matching them with climate-resilient design opportunities;

3. Integration of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The management of different types of data in the same working environment is a value proposition related to the potentiality of streamlining the design and planning process basing on the assessment of social, economic, and environmental co-benefits associated with climate-resilient development strategies and on the survey of community-based assets.

The methodology is oriented to foster processes of co-design and co-production generating a collaborative environment in which the dialogue between different stakeholders can facilitate the adoption of design and planning solutions desirable for the multiple actors engaged.

Cost: No funding required

11.2.1 Software Requirements

None (the tool is a guideline)

11.2.2 Data Requirements

None (the tool is a guideline)

11.2.3 Expertise Requirements

None (the tool is a guideline)

11.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

None (the tool is a guideline)

11.2.5 Tool Use Context

UCCRN UDCWs have been carried out since 2015 based on the climate-resilient design principles and methodological process introduced by the Urban Planning and Urban Design working group within the Second Assessment Report on Climate Change and Cities (ARC3.2).

11.2.6 Tool Limitations

None (the tool is a guideline)

11.2.7 City Journey

The scope of the tool is to provide multi-scale and urban planning and design guidance from strategic/conceptual level, to master planning and neighbourhood scale design.

The methodology helps to align climate goals with local stakeholders and community needs and priorities, connecting carbon neutrality, adaptation and environmental justice goals. The UDCW methodology includes a 4-step iterative process supported by specify tools (see UDCW Simulation toolkit and UDCW Facilitation toolkit), providing a fully quantitative and spatialized analysis of climate benefits of co-designed planning/design scenarios in relation to climate projections downscaled to the urban climate and other socio-economic and environmental co-benefits.

The tool is intended to be used by technical planning department in cities and planning/design practitioners.

11.2.8 Key Principles

Climate resilient development: The integrated action concurrently targeting carbon neutrality, climate adaptation and improved well-being of humans and non-human species living in cities. Such an ambitious holistic approach requires the development of innovative design methods that can handle the complexity of the information needed to guide sustainable urban regeneration and retrofitting strategies through participatory co-design practices in multi-stakeholder environments, as well as to manage the technological and environmental solutions in a multi-scale perspective. Cities represent in this sense the main field of experimentation of innovative and climate resilient design principles and methods.

Integrated Design Strategies: Utilised for creating sustainable and resilient communities that can adapt and thrive in the changing global conditions, meet carbon-reduction goals, provide new public spaces and facilities in relation to community priorities, by configuring or retrofitting compact and mixed-use eco-districts. The proposed design method is process-oriented and focuses on sequential and iterative steps bringing to projects' implementation through a multi-disciplinary and multi-scale approach.

11.2.9 Core Terms

Multi-Scale Climate Risk Assessment: impacts of slow-onset changes and extreme events in cities are too often assessed through coarse information at territorial scale that is not able to capture the effect of urban transformation. Key Performance Indicators adopted are often not spatialized, and when they are, there is a lack of connection among the indicators adopted at city scale with those applied to assess interventions at neighbourhood and building-open spaces scale, heavily impacting on the ability of actually meeting carbon neutrality, adaptation and environmental justice role throughout the often fragmented (temporally and jurisdictionally) process from strategic planning to implementation. The UDCW methodology provide a multi-scale climate risk assessment that allows to overcome these limits providing a set of harmonized and spatialized indicators across spatial scales.

Adaptation/Mitigation Strategies Assessment: scenario-based analysis of different possible planning and design scenarios (at city and/or neighbourhood scale), focused on quantitative indicators (see UDCW simulation toolkit).

Social, Economic, Environmental Co-Benefits Assessment: outcome of the UDCW participatory process, based on stakeholders' engagement, knowledge sharing and priorities mapping and the co-design of climate-resilient urban development strategies and solutions (see UDCW Facilitation toolkit), based on quanti/qualitative indicators reflecting needs of local stakeholders and communities.

11.2.10 Related Standards

- [ISO 37123:2019](#) Sustainable cities and communities Indicators for resilient cities: This document defines and establishes definitions and methodologies for a set of indicators on resilience in cities. This document is applicable to any city, municipality or local government that undertakes to measure its performance in a comparable and verifiable manner, irrespective of size or location. Maintaining, enhancing and accelerating progress towards improved city services and quality of life is fundamental to the definition of a resilient city, so this document is intended to be implemented in conjunction with [ISO 37120](#). This document follows the principles set out in ISO 37101, and can be used in conjunction with this and other strategic frameworks.

- UDCW Simulation toolkit (10.3)

- UDCW Facilitation toolkit 10.3).

11.2.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The methodology focuses on sequential and iterative phases that lead to the development of the project through the multi-disciplinary and multi-scale approach below. These are implemented with the support of UCCRN-EDU multidisciplinary experts and urban stakeholders, defining an intervention model that combines knowledge-sharing and co-design actions with urban decision-makers and local communities together with the development of simulations based on computational design tools to control the main indicators that determine the performance of buildings and open spaces in relation to climatic stress conditions.

Table 23: Step by step guide for UDCW Methodology.

1. Climate/microclimate analysis mapping identifies urban areas most affected by extreme events and seasonal variations, including local climate projections, as preliminary project information. Historical climate data and Regional Climate Models are processed through simulation models integrated into different design tools: GIS systems for city/district-level analyses, providing as output urban heat hotspots and flood zones; parametric 3D modelling tools (Rhinoceros+Grasshopper) assess technical solutions at the block/building scale, integrating climate-resilience aspects with other green building and environmental design criteria and benchmarks.

2. Collaborative mapping and co-design aims at assessing the quality of urban spaces and combining climate-related considerations with needs and expectations of local communities. Innovative stakeholder engagement methods (e.g. collaborative mapping, gamification and co-design through R3), involving residents, local administrations, neighbourhood and category associations, allow a shared reading of the main critical aspects of the urban system in relation to environmental, functional-spatial and socio-economic aspects. The synthesis of the results outlines a picture of shared needs and possible divergence elements between categories of stakeholders to integrate in the project.

3. Planning and design is based on a critical review of the information collected to identify synergies and trade-offs that can be implemented in relation to the planning initiatives envisaged by the local authorities. Urban plans and building regulations define the limits within which to develop the most appropriate technical-design strategies and solutions to achieve the set of objectives. Visual tools will link the multiple factors orienting local policy and transformative actions and possible meta-design layouts to support the production of innovative solutions addressing climate change impacts while increasing environmental quality in cities.

4. Post-intervention evaluation is intended as a sequence of activities to evaluate the benefits of the proposed solutions in terms of microclimate, energy and environmental performance, as well as compliance with community priorities. The tools include instruments for simulation-driven/indicator-based scenario comparisons, and for gathering direct feedback from residents and local stakeholders

11.3 UDCW-Urban Design Climate Workshop/Facilitation Toolkit

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools that allow to engage different typologies of city actors (experts: decision makers, city officials, planning/design practitioners; and non-experts: third sector and citizens) in a co-created climate resilient design process.

Cities can benefit from the toolkit to trigger knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context. The tools facilitate communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridge complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge.

The tools are conceived to foster the dialogue between experts and non-expert and to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens and as well with capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers.

The main objective is to create structured interactions with institutions, practitioners and civil society, leveraging a collective learning about climate-related issues and possible solutions.

The toolkit helps in contextualizing design solutions by establishing local priorities according to real needs and opportunities of a specific territory. When used in synergy with the UDCW Simulation toolkit, bottom-up data can be integrated to quantitative modelling of climate change impacts (heat and flood) and the assessment of mitigation/adaptation benefits and social, economic and environmental co-benefits of climate-resilient planning/design solutions.

The toolkit includes:

1. Collaborative mapping through analogic (boards/stickers) or digital (P-GIS Participatory Geographic Information System) tools (Collaborative mapping with experts and non-experts);
2. City visions and local needs matching (Priority mapping/co-design exercise with non-experts);
3. A Day in the life (Visioning exercise with experts and non-experts);
4. 3D neighbourhood configurator tool (co-design exercise with experts)

Cost: No funding required

11.3.1 Software Requirements

No specific software is required for the tools 2 and 3 of the toolkit (2. City visions and local needs matching; 3. A Day in the life).

For tool 1 (Collaborative mapping) if digital software for digital mapping is required (e.g. Open Street Maps, Google Maps) and additionally QGIS to deliver P-GIS Participatory Geographic Information System outcomes.

For tool 4 (3D neighbourhood configurator tool) the recommended software is Rhinoceros (McNeel, Version 6 or higher) for the configurator usage.

All the tools need to be used through workshops.

11.3.2 Data Requirements

Data are required only for tool 1 (Collaborative Mapping) to create baseline maps. Different kinds of information can be included in the baseline maps such as public services and facilities; transports; urban functions; historical and cultural landmarks; population; land use; building typologies; other typologies depending on data produced by researchers or cities.

These data are optional, as the mapping can be done as well just using satellite imagery data sources.

Data Format for baseline maps: KML/KMZ; txt.; ESRI Shapefile; DBF or CSV; raster images (.tiff; .jpeg; .png).

11.3.3 Expertise Requirements

Facilitation skills are required to guide the interactions between a diversity of participants to the co-design and co-production activities in a workshop environment. Previous engagement with city actors or local communities would be an advantage to structure the use of tools and tailor them appropriately to the context. Preparatory meetings with local key contacts are also advised. The toolkit is flexible as it contains different typologies of exercises, and it can be customized by the expertise of the facilitators and typology of target audience.

Knowledge about climate risks in urban areas and planning/architectural knowledge is highly recommended. Specifically for the 4 components of the toolkit experts' skills can be detailed as follows:

1. Collaborative mapping: basic knowledge on usage of online tools for mapping recommendable and GIS expertise optional
2. City visions and local needs matching: basic knowledge on city models and design solutions (e.g. circular city, green and blue city, zero carbon city, 15 minutes city), visualization and graphic expertise advisable
3. A Day in the life: none
4. 3D Neighbourhood configurator tool: architectural 3D modelling recommendable (basic Grasshopper knowledge)

11.3.4 Potential Barriers to Use

A UCCRN expert (facilitator) to lead the activities is advisable or specific training for local experts should be developed for capacity building.

Engagement of a consistent number of participants for the workshops could be demanding for city administrative offices.

For the management of the outcomes from the collaborative mapping a GIS background is required to integrate data from different sources (bottom-up information from communities or scientific data).

11.3.5 Tool Use Context

The toolkit has been developed to complement quantitative analysis for climate assessments with qualitative information and to better contextualize planning and design solutions according to the specificity of local issues and potentialities. The tools serve to survey thick data and no expert knowledge often overlooked in design and planning for urban resilience. The UDCW facilitation toolkit can be used at city level in planning departments or by private firms for engagement processes, co-design and public consultations. In terms of city governance, it can contribute to participatory planning, inclusive spatial decision-making and collective learning. It can contribute to drive spatial justice outcomes at procedural and recognitional level.

11.3.6 Tool Limitations

The tool requires a preparatory phase aimed at engaging relevant stakeholders and community representatives that will be involved in the workshop activities. A limited number of engaged participants results in a limited quality of final outcomes. Inclusiveness and representativeness of different population groups need to be ensured during the whole process of the toolkit use.

11.3.7 City Journey

The UDCW facilitation toolkit can be used at different stages of a City's Journey as the variety of tools can be flexible depending on the purpose of their use. They are particularly effective for mapping priorities at start of a project and at the stage of the idea formulation (Tool 1,2,3,4). Collaborative mapping (1) can be also useful in the follow up of a project implementation to verify effects of the interventions or urban policies. A Day in the life (3) can support effectively the up taking of everyday practices of sustainability through visioning and engagement.

11.3.8 Key Principles

Co-production: Involves the active engagement of various stakeholders in the creation, implementation, and evaluation of policies, projects, or services, fostering a sense of ownership and shared responsibility.

Co-design: A collaborative process where diverse stakeholders, including community members, architects, planners and experts in various fields, work together to develop solutions and create designs that address specific challenges or objectives.

Facilitation: The act of guiding a group through a process, ensuring effective communication, collaboration, and decision-making while maintaining a neutral stance as a facilitator.

Inclusive Community and Stakeholder Engagement: The process of involving community members, organizations, and other stakeholders in discussions, decision-making, and actions related to urban design and climate resilience.

Bottom-up Information: First-hand insights into the built environment, social dynamics, and community needs, informing urban design and planning processes with on-the-ground perspectives.

Climate-Related Collective Learning: Refers to the collaborative process through which individuals, communities, organizations, and stakeholders collectively acquire, share, and integrate knowledge, experiences, and insights related to climate change challenges and potential responses.

Everyday Sustainable Practices: Actions, behaviours, and habits adopted by individuals, communities, and organizations in their daily lives to promote environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Examples are reducing energy consumption, minimizing waste generation, utilizing sustainable transportation modes, supporting local economies, and practicing responsible consumption and production patterns.

11.3.9 Core Terms

Participatory Exercises: Interactive activities or workshops designed to actively involve participants in the planning and decision-making process, allowing for diverse perspectives and ideas to emerge.

City Models: Representations of urban areas used for analysis, visualization, and planning purposes, ranging from physical scale models to digital simulations.

Climate-Related Risks: Potential adverse impacts or hazards resulting from climate change, such as extreme weather events, sea-level rise, and heatwaves, floods, landslides which can threaten urban infrastructure, ecosystems, and communities.

Urban Design Solutions for Climate-Resilience or Climate-Resilient Interventions: Strategies, approaches, interventions, and technical solutions at multiple scales aimed at enhancing the capacity of

cities to withstand and adapt to the impacts of climate change while promoting justice, sustainability and human well-being.

Collaborative Mapping: The process of creating maps or spatial representations in collaboration with various stakeholders to gather, share, and analyse information related to urban environments, resources, and vulnerabilities.

Participatory Geographic Information Systems: Integrates GIS technology with participatory approaches, allowing communities to collect, analyse, and visualize spatial data relevant to their needs and priorities.

Visioning: A process of collectively imagining and articulating a desired future state or vision for a city, guiding long-term planning efforts and inspiring action towards shared goals and aspirations.

Focus Group: A qualitative research method involving a small group of individuals selected based on specific criteria, brought together to discuss and provide feedback on a particular topic or issue.

Neighbourhood Walk: A participatory activity where stakeholders, including residents, planners, and experts, physically explore a specific neighbourhood or area to observe and assess its characteristics, assets, challenges, and opportunities.

Personas: Fictional representations of different user types or stakeholders involved in the urban design and planning process, created to better understand their perspectives, needs, and behaviours. Personas help designers and facilitators tailor solutions and engagement strategies to diverse audience groups, ensuring inclusivity and relevance in the planning process.

Co-Benefits Related to Climate-Resilient Design Solutions: Additional positive outcomes or advantages beyond the primary objective of enhancing climate resilience that result from implementing design solutions. These co-benefits may include improvements in public health, biodiversity conservation, social equity and spatial and environmental justice, cultural preservation, and overall quality of life.

11.3.10 Related Standards

There are no related standards

11.3.11 Step-by-Step Guide

The toolkit is composed by 4 tools designed to be used in workshops. Each of the 4 tools can be used standalone or in synergies depending by the target of the co-design and co-production activity, duration of the workshop and number of participants. The toolkit has a guideline to guide the potential users in managing the facilitation process and organizing the different steps of each participatory exercise.

Table 24: Step by step guide for UDCW-Urban Design Climate Workshop/Facilitation Toolkit.

1. Collaborative mapping:

Experts develop physical or digital maps with baseline information that can include qualitative and quantitative data (e.g., data on climate-related risks and other environmental risks, vulnerability of population, building typologies etc.). Through a focus group or a neighbourhood walk the engagement of participants is triggered. They are invited to develop a mapping exercise on physical maps (with stickers) to collect bottom-up data. These data are depending on the specific aim of the activity and on the specific local focus and issues to be interlinked with climate topics. Experts collect the data and

implement digital maps with both experts and non-experts' data to deliver a public platform of knowledge sharing available for communities and decision makers.

2. City visions and local needs matching:

Experts prepare posters and cards dedicated to city visions and potential design options. Local needs are surveyed through a focus group oriented to feed city visions with local perspectives while delivering to participants knowledge about climate resilient interventions.

3. A Day in the life exercise:

Experts set personas options developing with non-experts, participants a visioning exercise to understand potentialities of everyday practices of the sustainability and urban design options that can support them.

4. 3D neighbourhood configurator tool:

Experts prepare a set of solutions that will be combined by participants. The activity is conducted by UCCRN experts in collaboration with local experts and it is oriented to the evaluation of participants preferences and co-benefits related to climate-resilient design solutions. The result is a digital co-design outcome.

12 University of Cambridge

The University of Cambridge (UCAM) is one of the world's leading universities. Since 1209, Cambridge has been at the forefront of many significant scientific firsts - including the discovery of gravity and DNA as well as evolution to name a few. For UP2030, UCAM is represented by researchers from the Centre for Sustainable Development, established in 2000 following support provided by the Royal Academy of Engineering, to introduce concepts of sustainability over all their undergraduate engineering courses. The Centre has grown to encompass the delivery of a one-year full-time taught MPhil in Engineering for Sustainable Development and a research community currently covering sustainable development issues in the fields of water, urban flood management, infrastructure resilience, post-disaster recovery, international development, climate change mitigation and adaptation and system dynamic modelling of coupled resource management.

<https://www-csd.eng.cam.ac.uk/>

12.1 Carbon Budget Framework

This tool is currently in an early stage of development and will be entirely developed within UP2030. Therefore, some sections (such as the step-by-step guide) are less complete than would be so in the future when the tool is more developed.

Whilst many cities are working to reduce and eventually neutralise their 'organisational' carbon emissions, this is limited to carbon emissions produced through their operation. For a city system to maximise emissions reduction, accounting beyond traditional perceived scope of control is needed. An essential element to consider is the influence and power that local urban authorities possess in influencing the city beyond their immediate responsibilities. However, before a city can move beyond accounting and managing scope 1 and 2 emissions, an understanding and clarification of how carbon emission data is currently produced, stored, and utilised is essential. The Carbon Budget Framework supports cities in mapping the flows of carbon emission data by applying a wider systems-view of a city than traditionally used in carbon reporting.

The framework is designed to primarily benefit city authorities in two ways along their journey towards reducing and removing their emissions:

1. Clarification of current urban carbon emission data and its uses: Not only is the task of moving beyond scopes 1 and 2 and carbon accounting complex, so is the contemporary nature of urban carbon emission data and its uses within the city system. It is anticipated that the framework will clarify and better integrate already existing data sets and collection practices into the city governance. It is intended that this will lead to an enhanced understanding of how carbon is, and can be better managed, within the city itself. The intention is to develop a foundation from which carbon management based on the view of a city as a system of systems can be enacted.
2. Expanding the management of city carbon emissions beyond the direct influence of city authorities: Growing out of this better understanding, the carbon budget framework is centred around applying these insights to the city as a whole, across the boundaries of different actors, systems and sectors – with the intention of developing holistic, joined-up, citywide carbon management. This will help cities to more effectively cut their carbon emissions and allow them to better contribute towards the fight against climate change.

Ultimately, the framework is built on the hypothesis that a clearer the understanding of current data practices and flows will create a more informed view of emission reduction potential across the whole city, which will lead to a more effective, holistic pursuit of carbon neutrality.

Cost: No funding required

12.1.1 Software Requirements

No specific software is required as the maps are produced through workshops, although visualisation software such as Miro or X.Mind could be used to produce digital versions of the maps.

12.1.2 Data Requirements

Carbon emission inventory (scope 1 and 2) - this can be either directly monitored or through estimating emissions.

12.1.3 Expertise Requirements

There are no essential skills needed to use this approach, but experience and knowledge with collecting or utilising emission data, as well as good general IT competency would be advantageous.

The output would be "owned" by someone who has a senior level of responsibility for carbon reduction, and an interest in this being effectively achieved across an organisation, not just in one department.

Development of a baseline requires consultation with stakeholders within the city administration to inform the development of the baseline data map.

12.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

It will need buy-in from the local authorities that this is a useful management tool.

A lack of availability of emission data.

12.1.5 Tool Use Context

This approach will be utilised to assess the use of carbon emission data across a city administration.

The approach is primarily designed to be used by city authorities, particularly the government departments responsible for utilising carbon emission data - however, this does not mean that non-city actors/stakeholders are excluded from participating.

12.1.6 Tool Limitations

This tool is currently envisaged to only conceptually map city authority emissions and not emissions from other data sources, although this could be developed in future versions.

The mapping process is currently done manually, rather than with specialist software. This is because of the early stage of development where the approach requires pilot testing.

12.1.7 City Journey

This approach is designed to be utilised after a city has created an initial inventory of carbon emission data and is seeking to utilise that insight in creating emission reduction policies.

12.1.8 Key Principles

Carbon Management: The assessment, reduction and removal of greenhouse gas emissions during the planning, optioneering, design, delivery, operation, use, end of life (and beyond) of new, or the management of existing, assets, networks and/or systems (PAS:2080).

Systems Thinking: A special consideration of the interrelations and connections between seemingly separate elements of the city, in order to create more holistic approaches to reducing carbon emissions.

Desiloisation: Supporting the sharing of data and insight between different groups, departments and organisations (which do not so already, but could) to provide a wider range of information to support more holistic approaches to reducing carbon emissions.

Urban Carbon Management: The governance and systemic integration of the planning, design and operation of all activities relating to the assessment, reduction and removal of carbon emissions produced within, and through the consumption patterns of a city or urban area.

12.1.9 Core Terms

Carbon Emissions (Greenhouse Gas):⁷

carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃)

Carbon Emission Scopes:⁸

- Scope 1 GHG emissions from sources located within the city boundary
- Scope 2 GHG emissions occurring as a consequence of the use of grid-supplied electricity, heat, steam and/or cooling within the city boundary
- Scope 3 All other GHG emissions that occur outside the city boundary as a result of activities taking place within the city boundary

Carbon Budget: Carbon budgets are emission reduction targets often utilised by cities. They are particularly appropriate for use in the urban realm, given they follow the same logic as financial budgets, which are utilised within the governing of a city, replacing budget with carbon emissions.

Urban Carbon Emission Ontology: A framework designed to holistically consider the totality of different elements associated with urban carbon emission reduction and management. Rather than dividing urban carbon emissions into different, and often siloed, sectors, the purpose of this ontology is to link the assessment and reduction of them in a manner which spans across the whole city – emphasising the characteristics of the emissions and approaches designed to reduce them, themselves, rather than solely the source from which they are produced. The ontology is composed of seven elements:

- Investigation: Methods, approaches, tools and concepts relating to analysing urban carbon emissions.
- Emission Sources: Sources of urban carbon emissions.
- Form of Emission: The type of emissions and particles.
- Urban Environment: The physical elements of the city - both built and natural.
- Transition: Approaches conceived to reduce carbon emissions.
- Governance: Policies, Directives and Legislation concerning city development and carbon emission reduction.

- Context: That which indirectly influences the production of carbon emissions – such as social, demographic or economic factors.

Process Map: A process map is a visualising method to illustrate the flows of information and, in our case data, within an organisation. This method will form the basis of our carbon emission data flow maps.

12.1.10 Related Standards

Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Inventories (GPC): The global leading standard for supporting cities to create carbon emission inventories, used by over 12,000 cities to become members of the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy programme.

PAS2080: Carbon Management in Buildings and Infrastructure (2023): Publicly Available Specification 2080, a standard developed by the British Standards Institute, outlines a practical process to realize low-carbon outcomes by providing a ‘common process for the built environment value chain on how to manage whole life carbon in projects and programmes of work’.

Kyoto Protocol (1997): The Kyoto Protocol first identified the six forms of gas which make up greenhouse gasses (See section 10). These gasses are the root cause of climate change and are those to be monitored within cities.

12.1.11 Step-by-Step Guide

These steps will be completed by the UCAM team for pilot testing

Table 25: Step by step guide for Carbon Budget Framework.

1. Data gathering exercise with key stakeholders across the organisation structured around the urban carbon emission ontology. Ideally this will involve representatives from across key organisational departments where there is some responsibility for decision making with respect to carbon emissions.
2. Develop an initial “carbon data” map of the organisation using readily available software for creating process diagrams. This will be in the form of a bespoke process flow diagram that tracks data/information flow through the following steps: (1) data and information sources (2) management systems and repositories (3) people/teams (4) application – processes/decisions/actions taken.
3. Validate the carbon data map with organisational representatives – most effective if this achieved through hosting a workshop.
4. Use the output map as a tool for developing evidence for how interventions will improve organisational capacity for effective urban carbon management.

13 Conclusion

This document has served to demonstrate the range of tools related to digital planning and design for climate neutral cities within UP2030, by providing an overview of 22 tools from 10 providers. The ultimate intention of this deliverable is to assist cities in selecting the right tool for them.

Each tool provider listed above is a partner within the UP2030 project and has provided the information presented in this document. A survey was distributed during Q2 2024, which formed the structure of the descriptions provided throughout, a process conducted by the University of Cambridge (UCAM) team. The tools were reviewed by the UCAM team to assess the type of support offered by each tool, as well as the potential barriers to, and limitations of, use.

Overall, the tools included in this deliverable each serve to enhance decision-making capabilities within city authorities. However, this is conducted along different lines. Whilst some support improving the development and implementation of mitigation approaches towards combatting climate change, others focus on adaptation and enhancing the resilience of cities when faced with its effects. Other tools revolve around engagement and supporting the integration of diverse stakeholders in the decision-making process, be this through engaging the community or better aligning those who work within the city. Another theme which has emerged is the pursuit of improving data use when making climate neutrality decisions and, to conclude, a range of tools support the design of neutrality approaches.

To reiterate a point raised in the introductory section, whilst this guide is intended to serve as an overview of each of the tools, this version is the first of two, with limitations in information availability concerning some elements of each tool's function being present. To this end there are several elements which have not been fully realised in this version but shall be in the final deliverable (due month 36). Going forward the lack of case study examples of the tools being utilised within cities will be rectified vis-à-vis collaborations between the tool providers and partner cities. This will also remedy the variation amongst the step-by-step guides proposed by the tool providers in this version.

Another area which will be attended to is the degree of variation between the detail of the tools themselves. Currently, some of the above tools are in an early stage of development, whilst others are fully mature; this gap in implementation experience will be assuaged come the time of the second deliverable. For the final deliverable, each tool will be presented in, and to, the same standard, where prominent use of process/system diagrams, use case studies, detailed step-by-step guides and, where appropriate screenshots of tool use will be presented. Tools will also be aligned with other frameworks currently undergoing development, such as the Planning Cycle developed by TU Delft and the UP2030 '5UPs'.

The tools presented here embody a multiplicity of approaches to support and enable better climate neutrality actions from a diverse range of providers who each possess a deep repository of expertise which has been leveraged to produce these novel, leading-edge tools and approaches. Depending upon the context for their use, each of these tools is in good stead to enhance any city which desires to implement them. This guide has been created to support the process of selecting the right tools for such cities.

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14 Appendix

14.1.1 Appendix 1

Deltares CRCTool step-by-step screenshots:

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- Pluvial Flooding
- Heat Stress
- Drought

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14.1.2 Appendix 2

Table 26: UCCRN Data table.

Input	File Type	Base Attributes	Detailed Attributes	Type of Object
Land Use / Land Cover	Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage	Land use class (current city conditions): 1. Agricultural areas 2. Bare soil 3. Buildings 4. Built open spaces 5. Railways 6. Roads 7. Outdoor sports facilities 8. Forested areas 9. Green areas (non forested) 10. Water	Detailed information for some land use classes (see Base Attributes): crop type (1), vegetation type (8, 9), paving material (4,6)	Polygon
Protected areas (Green Infrastructure core areas)	Shapefile, GeoTiff	Natura 2000 attributes	-	Polygon, Raster
NDVI (Green Infrastructure ecological quality)	GeoTiff	NDVI attributes	-	Raster
Trees	Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage	Tree canopy diameter range [m]	Tree canopy diameter [m] Total height [m] Trunk height [m] Species (e.g. pine, maple, etc.) Maintenance required (soft pruning, heavy pruning) Planting site (park/garden, paved area) Foliage color (light, med., dark) Trunk diameter [cm]	Single objects (point) or groups of objects (Polygon)
Buildings	Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage	Height Range [m]	Height [m] N. of storeys Property type (public, private, mixed) Use type (residential, commercial, industrial, office,	Polygon

			etc.) Construction typology (masonry, concrete, timber, steel, etc.) Year of construction (approx.) Roof color (light, med., dark) Roof type (flat, sloped) Roof material (tiles, membrane, photovoltaic, green roof, etc.) Percentage of openings HVAC specification (including generation and distribution systems) Occupancy rate	
Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	GeoTiff, Floating Point Raster File, csv	-	-	Raster
Digital Surface Model (DSM)	GeoTiff, USGS DEM, Floating Point Raster File, csv	-	-	Raster
Population distribution	Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage, csv, xls	N. of people Age distribution Income distribution	School enrollment rate, unemployment rate, crime rate	Point or polygon per census tract (or the smallest spatial scale available)
Territorial River Basins	Geotiff, Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage	Low Resolution Watersheds (from EU DEM)	High Resolution Watersheds (from Local Datasets)	Polygon, Raster
Hydrological risk	Geotiff, Shapefile, GeoJSON, Geopackage	River flood risk areas	River flood risk zonation Expected Water Depths for identified return periods	Polygon, Raster